

Project no. 044189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

6.1 Publishable Final Activity report PEPEIRA

Period covered: from February 01, 2007 to January 31, 2010

Date of preparation: April 2010

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Project coordinator name: Dr. R.A.A. van der Vlugt

Project coordinator organisation name: Plant Research International

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis*

www.pepeira.wur.nl

Project coördinator:

Dr. R.A.A. van der Vlug
Plant Research International
P.O. Box 16
6700 AA WAGENINGEN
The Netherlands
P: +31-317- 48 06 75
F: +31-317-41 80 94
E-mail: rene.vandervlugt@wur.nl

Project summary

PEPEIRA is an RTD activity aimed at developing an EU-wide Pest Risk Assessment (PRA) for Pepino mosaic virus (PepMV). The proposal will investigate the epidemiology and economic impact of PepMV in order to allow a robust and scientifically-justified assessment of the risk posed by this pathogen to the European tomato industry. This includes a true assessment of the economic impact on tomato crops growing in Member States with different climatic and market conditions and the role of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV. The project will also address the increased risk posed by new, biologically and genetically distinct, strains of PepMV that have appeared in Europe and elsewhere recently and have the potential to be far more damaging than the original tomato strain. The proposal will also address the issue of developing validated diagnostic protocols, to be published via EPPO, that can be used with confidence by National Plant Protection Organisations (NPPOs) within the EU and laboratories in other countries that trade with the EU. In addition to a strong and focussed science program, the proposal also mobilises an impressive consortium, including all EU laboratories with a proven track record of PepMV research, with extensive plant virus and plant health expertise from all Member States where PepMV poses a potential risk. Consultation with the principle stakeholders (Plant Health Standing Committee, DG SANCO, growers and seed companies etc.) throughout the life of the project is given paramount importance. Adoption of the new PRA will allow EU Plant Health services to develop, via Council Directive 2000/29/EC, a consensus on appropriate measures to prevent PepMV becoming a significant threat to the EU tomato industry. This in turn will help to prevent any negative impact on the sustainability of European horticulture and other negative economic and social effects associated with the further establishment of this disease.

Project objective(s)

Over-all objective: To deliver increased knowledge of the epidemiology and economic impact of *Pepino mosaic virus* in the EU context, such that an updated rigorous Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) can be performed to underpin the existing legislation and to help the consideration of any necessary amendments.

The main scientific and technical objective of this work is to develop a robust PRA to determine the risk to European protected tomato crops posed by PepMV, which is currently the subject of EU emergency measures. In order to achieve this, there is a need to:

- Assess the economic impact that PepMV can have on commercial tomato crops grown under different climatic and cultural conditions. This will be achieved by completing commercial glasshouse trials at four geographically distinct locations within the EU using a standardized variety and a standardized tomato isolate of the virus. The results will be used to assess the economic impact of PepMV in different geographical locations and at different industry production standards.
- Examine the threat of new virus genotypes by conducting studies on the effects that these new variants and strains have on tomato plants and other agronomically important Solanaceous crops.
- Obtain new scientific data and use these in conjunction with the existing data to further our understanding of disease epidemiology by studying the incidence of different PepMV isolates and strains over Europe and determining the risk of virus transmission through seeds.
- Model the potential impact PepMV could have on the European tomato industry should this pathogen become established;
- Finally, harmonised risk management strategies and contingency plans are required to deal with this pathogen within the EU. This will be achieved through the development of a standardized EPPO detection protocol for use by NPPOs, inspection services and industry.

Project consortium partners

PEPEIRA is a collaboration between 20 laboratories and institution involved in or dealing with Plant Health from 17 European countries. The consortium consists of the following partners:

Partner 1 (PRI: coordinator)

Dr R van der Vlugt
Plant Research International
P.O. Box 16, NL-6700 AA Wageningen, The Netherlands
Phone: +31 (0) 317 480675
E-mail: Rene.vandervlugt@wur.nl

Partner 2 (Fera)

Dr R Mumford
Food & Environmental Research Agency
Sand Hutton, York, YO41 1LZ, United Kingdom
Phone: +44 (0) 1904 462140
E-mail: rick.mumford@fera.gsi.gov.uk

Dr J Peters

Food & Environmental Research Agency
Sand Hutton, York, YO41 1LZ, United Kingdom
Phone: +44 (0) 1904 462140
E-mail: jeff.peters@fera.gsi.gov.uk

Partner 3 (UPM)

Prof. Dr. F García-Arenal
E.T.S.I Agrónomos, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Avenida Complutense s/n, 28040, Madrid, Spain
Phone: +34 913365768
E-mail: fernando.garciaarenal@upm.es

Partner 4 (UPV)

Prof. Dr. Jorda-Gutierrez
Instituto Agrofestal Del Mediterraneo
Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain
Phone: +34 963879255
E-mail: mjordag@eaf.upv.es

Ana Alfaro-Fernández
Instituto Agrofestal Del Mediterraneo
Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain
Phone: +34 963879259
E-mail: analfer1@doctor.upv.es

Carmen Cordoba-Selles
Instituto Agrofestal Del Mediterraneo
Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain
Phone: +34 963879259
E-mail: mcorsel@eaf.upv.es

Partner 5 (CsM-MgSzH)

Dr. B. Gábor
Csongrád Megyei Mezőgazdasági
Szakigazgatási Hivatal
Növény- és Talajvédelmi Igazgatóság
Rárósi út 110, PO Box 99, 6801,
Hódmezővásárhely, Hungary
Phone: + 36 62 535773

Partner 6 (AU)

Dr. S.L. Nielsen
University of Aarhus, Faculty of Agricultural
Sciences
Department of Integrated Pest Management
Forsøgsvej 1, DK-4200, Slagelse, Denmark
Phone: +45 89 99 35 00
E-mail: steenl.nielsen@agrsci.dk

Partner 7 (WUR Glastuinbouw)

Dr. C.C.M.M. Stijger
Wageningen University and Researchcentre,
Greenhouse Horticulture
PO box 20, 2665 MV, Bleiswijk, The
Netherlands
Phone: +31 317 485671
E-Mail: Ineke.stijger@wur.nl

Partner 8 (CRA)

Dr. L.Tomasoli
Istituto Sperimentale per la Patologia
Vegetale
Via Carlo Giuseppe Bertero, 22, 00156,
Roma, Italy
Phone : +39 0682070292
E-mail: laura.tomassoli@entecra.it

Partner 9 (LNPV)

M. X. Tassus
Laboratoire National de la Protection des
Végétaux
Rue Dixmèras 7, 49044, Cedex 1, Angers,
France
Phone: +33 (0) 2 41 72 32 40
E-mail: xavier.tassus@agriculture.gouv.fr

Partner 10 (ST)

Drs. I. Hanssen
Scientia Terrae Research Institute
Fortsesteenweg 30a, 2860 Sint-Katelijne-
Waver, Belgium
Phone: + 32 15 30 55 90
E-mail: iha@scientiaterrae.org

Partner 11 (NIB)

Prof. Dr. M. Ravnikar
National Institute of Biology
Vecna pot 111, SI-1001 Ljubljana, Slovenia
Phone: + 386 1 4233388
E-mail: Maja.Ravnikar@nib.si

Partner 12 (ARC)

Dr. K. Petrusis
Agricultural Research Centre (ARC)
Estonia
Phone: + 37 2 6729161
E-mail: karme.petrutis@pmk.agri.ee

Partner 13 (ARI)

Dr. L. Papayiannis
Agricultural Research Institute (ARI)
Athalassa, PO Box 22016, 1516, Nicosia,
Cyprus
Phone: + 35 722403203
E-mail: l.papayiannis@arinet.ari.gov.cy

Partner 14 (IOR)

Prof. Dr. H. Pospieszny
Institute for Plant Protection (IOR)
W. Wegorka 20, 60-318, Poznan, Poland
Phone: + 48 618649094
E-mail: H.Pospieszny@ior.poznan.pl

Partner 15 (BPI)

Dr. C. Varveri
Benaki Phytopathological Institute
8 St. Delta street, 14561, Kifissia, Greece
Phone: + 30 210 2128036
E-mail: c.varveri@bpi.gr

Partner 16 (BioForsk)

Dr. Dag-Ragnar Blystad
Bioforsk, Norwegian Inst. For Agricultural
and Environmental Research
Høgskoleveien 7, N-1432, Aas, Norway
Phone: + 47 908 72 588
E-mail: dag-ragnar.blystad@bioforsk.no

Partner 17 (PPI)

Prof. Dr. D. Hristova
Plant Protection Institute (PPI)
2230 Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
Phone: + 35 9 721 6 60 61
E-mail: di_hristova@yahoo.com

Partner 18 (UTAD)

Prof. Dr. A.M. Nazaré Pereira
Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto
Douro (UTAD)
Departamento de Protecção de Plantas,
5000-801 Vila Real Portugal
Phone: + 351 259350506
E-mail: anazare@utad.pt

Partner 19 (PPS)

Dr. J.W. Roenhorst
Plant Protection Service
PO Box 9102, 6700 HC, Wageningen, The
Netherlands
Phone: + 31 317 496850
E-mail: j.w.roenhorst@minlnv.nl

Partner 20 (JKI)

Dr.H.J. Vetten
Julius Kühn Institute, Federal Research
Centre for Cultivated Plants (JKI)
Messeweg 11-12
38104 Braunschweig, Germany
Phone: +49 513 2993720
E-mail: heinrich-josef.vetten@jki.bund.de

1. Project execution

The PEPEIRA project is divided into four work packages (WPs):

- WP 1: Project coordination and management
- WP 2: PepMV trials & economic impact
- WP 3: PepMV characteristics and occurrence
- WP 4: Risk assessment and diagnostic protocol

WP 1: Project coordination and management

Deliverables

- 1.1. 3x collated periodic activity and management reports
- 1.2. 1x final project report
- 1.3. Website, including a secure area accessible by all partners and a public area for general dissemination
- 1.4. Kick-off meeting, 6th Month stakeholder meeting/30th Month symposia programs

WP 1 deals with project coordination management. The project is coordinated by partner #1 (PRI) who, together with partners 2, 6 and 20 form the project management committee and partners # 8, 9, 19 and 20 form the steering committee.

The first year periodic activity report and management reports were compiled by the coordinator and administrative assistance and submitted to the EU in March 2008, the second year reports in March 2009 and the third year and final project reports were compiled in May 2010.

The coordinator and the project management committee (PMC) met officially three times: once in May 2007 at the start of the project at the kick-off meeting in Wageningen, The Netherlands, the second time in September 2008 in York, half-way through the project to discuss progress and the last time during the final meeting in Wageningen in January 2010. All PMC members were however present at the other annual project meetings; March 2008 in Valencia, Spain and February 2009 in Larnaca, Cyprus. Interim scientific meetings were held in August 2008 (Hungary) and September 2009 (UK) where the 4 partners running the glasshouse trials under WP2 met with each other and the coordinator to discuss trial results, progress and future planning.

In March 2009 Dr René van der Vlugt as coordinator and Dr Jeff Peters (FERA, partner 2) had a meeting with Dr Baker, the coordinator of the EU project Pratique at FERA. The meeting was meant to inform each other about the two projects and investigate possible future collaboration especially with respect to the PRA to be written in the Pepeira project.

The Standing Committee on Plant Health of the Commission was informed by the Coordinator during its meetings on May 27, 2009 on the content of the project and the progress already made. The SCPH as one of the customers of the project will finally benefit from the results (Pest risk analysis, testing procedure).

A public website was set up to inform the general public on the project and its results (www.pepeira.wur.nl). In addition a secure share-point site was initiated for all project partners as well as the EU-scientific project officer. This share point allowed the partners to submit material and share project results and gave them unlimited access to project data and reports.

During the last year of the project the public website was restyled to make it more accessible and allow registration for the Pepeira stakeholders symposium that was organized in January 2010.

This scientific conference ('Pepino mosaic virus; The European perspective', Wageningen, January 22, 2010) took place in Wageningen on January 22, 2010. As such it was an important deliverable of

the project (deliverable 1.4)-not only to inform stakeholders on project results but also to discuss, and exchange views with them on PepMV damage and management. Although in the original project proposal foreseen at month 30, the meeting was organized in month 36. This was considered necessary because this date allowed for more complete project results to be disseminated to the stakeholders. The rather late availability of field trial data (November 2009) did not allow for an earlier draft version of the PRA than early January 2010. This draft PRA formed an important input in the discussions with the stakeholders on the possible management options for PepMV.

A total of 46 stakeholders (excluding the project partners) from 7 different European countries participated in the meeting. Stakeholders from all major groups involved in PepMV were present: 10 from policy, including DG Sanco, EPPO and national plant protection agencies, science, the seed industry, plant growers, European testing laboratories and consultants.

Figure 1: Distribution of the different professional categories over the participants that responded to the questionnaire.

The stakeholders were informed about the project's results through lectures from the various Work Packages leaders and in a joint afternoon session discussed two important questions:

1. What is the damage caused by PepMV and who is affected by it?
2. What management options are available for the different stakeholders and are they feasible?

From these discussions valuable information was obtained on how different stakeholders viewed PepMV and possible management of this disease. Following sometimes intense discussions a number of conclusions were drawn:

- PepMV causes substantial direct and indirect damage and has a significant impact on the European tomato industry.
- Control is possible in seeds and legislation for PepMV on seeds (and possibly young plants) is necessary.
- Strict hygienic measures are very important but may not prevent infections.
- Monitoring programmes contribute to the control of the disease but more detailed knowledge about the major pathways is still required for effective management.

In addition all participants were asked to complete a questionnaire of PepMV. The results of this questionnaire gave a better view on how the different professions that have to deal with PepMV view the disease the problems it causes. This information and the information obtained from the afternoon discussion was used in the final version of the PRA.

Table 1: Deliverables List WP1

List all deliverables, giving date of submission and any proposed revision to plans.

Del. no.	Deliverable name	Work package no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Estimated indicative person-months	Used indicative person-months *)	Lead contractor
1.1	3x collated periodic activity and management reports	1	M12, 24, 3634	M12, 24, 36	1.9	1.9	1
1.2	1x final project report	1	M36	M34	3	3	1
1.3	Website, including a secure area accessible by all partners and a public area for general dissemination	1	M6	M6	1	1	1
1.4	6 th Month stakeholder meeting/30 th Month symposia programs	1	M36	M36	1	1	1
1.5	Project presentation	1	M6	M6	1	1	1

*) if available

Table 2: Milestones List WP1

List all milestones, giving date of achievement and any proposed revision to plans.

Milestone no.	Milestone name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Lead contractor
1.1	Successful organisation of 6 Monthly R&D meetings.	1	M6, 12, 18, 24, 30 & 36	M6, 12, 18, 24, 30 & 36	1
1.2	Successful organisation of 6 th Month stakeholder meeting/30 th Month symposia.	1	M6 & 30	M6 & 36	1
1.3	Set up a secure website and initiate population with information and results.	1	M6	M6	1

All WP 1 deliverables and milestones have been met.

WP 2: PepMV trials & economic impact

Deliverables

- 2.1. Completed glasshouse trials over two seasons on four different locations
- 2.2. Assessment of impact of PepMV on infected tomato crops
- 2.3. Econometric model for assessing economic impact
- 2.4. Cost benefit analysis of PepMV control measures

WP 2 deals with field and glasshouse trials to assess the damage and economic impact of PepMV on late infected tomato crops.

Four partner institutes from Hungary, Netherlands, Spain and UK (Table 1) set up replicate greenhouse trials over two full seasons to assess the economic impact of *Pepino mosaic virus* (PepMV) in late-infected tomato crops. Previous research from the UK has suggested that PepMV has a significant effect on fruit quality and has no overall effect on fruit yield (Spence et al. 2006), while other EU countries reported either effects on yield or a limited impact of PepMV infection on both fruit yield and quality. It is unclear whether the observed effects on yield and quality apply to tomato crops grown in all EU-member states. Replicate trials were carried out in four major tomato producing areas to assess the possible damage of PepMV under different environmental and cropping conditions to provide an EU-wide perspective. In these greenhouse trials, we determined the effects of the mild PepMV isolate *1066* and the aggressive PepMV isolate *PCH-06/104* on yield and quality on tomato plants. These isolates cover the impact ranging from a mild PepMV infection to a worse case scenario. The isolate *1066* belongs to the European tomato strain, while the isolate *PCH-06/104* belongs to the Chile2 strain of PepMV. Trial data were combined with results from a cost-benefit analysis to allow an assessment of the possible overall economic impact of PepMV in each EU-member state.

Table 1. Participants in the PepMV greenhouse trials

Partner	Institute	Location	Country
2	Food & Environment Research Agency (Fera)	York	UK
4	Universidad Politénica de Valencia	Valencia	Spain
5	Csongrád Megyei Mezőgazdasági SZakigazgatási Hivatal (CsM-MgSZH)	Hódmezővásárhely	Hungary
7	Wageningen UR Glastuinbouw (WUR)	Bleiswijk	The Netherlands

Materials and methods

Replicate greenhouse trials were carried out during two growing seasons. Crops were infected with the mild PepMV isolate *1066* and with the aggressive isolate *PCH-06/104* in the first and second growing season, respectively. These trials were conducted following a standardized set-up, while tomato plants were grown according to the local commercial practice of each participating partner country. Conformity between sites was ensured by using standardized protocols to manage the trials and to collect the data. Inter-site variation was minimized by holding a workshop prior to the start of the first trial, which was held before the project kick-off meeting in the Netherlands (May 2007). An interim meeting was held in Hungary to review the progress made during the Hungarian trials in 2007, when the other trials had not yet started. This opportunity was used to make refinements to the initial protocols. A second interim meeting was held in York (UK) between the first and second growing season to discuss results from the first season and to evaluate the protocols.

Eventually, two different protocols were drafted by the workpackage leader (Partner 2) and circulated amongst the other partners involved in WP2. Revisions were made based on comments received and the final versions were circulated. The two protocols produced were: **1. Trials Monitoring Protocol**, which provided guidance on the monitoring of the virus infection, virus-related symptoms and fruit-set. **2. Quality Assessment Protocol**, which is based on Directive 790/2000 EC “Marketing Standard for tomatoes”, and provides guidance on how to assess the post-harvest crop yield and quality of the trials. This protocol defines criteria such as fruit size and quality. Advice from both industry and Horticulture Marketing Inspectors proved to be essential when drafting this protocol. Horticulture Marketing Inspectors are required to enforce Directive 790/2000 and hence have an excellent understanding of the boundaries between different fruit classes; a critical and highly subjective area.

Common trial design

The tomato cultivar Cedrico was cultivated in all trials in both growing seasons. Tomato plants were planted and grown according to the local commercial practice. Two treatments were assessed during both growing seasons, namely a PepMV infected treatment and a healthy control treatment. Both treatments were represented by four replicate plots that consisted of 20 tomato plants each. All Cedrico plants in the infected plots were mechanically inoculated with the *1066* isolate (first season) or the *PCH-06/104* isolate (second season). Partner 7 (the Netherlands) had grown tomato plants infected with these isolates and subsequently distributed infected leaves from these plants to the other partner institutes. They inoculated several cv. Cedrico plants in order to have a fresh source of inoculum available on site. Trial plants were subjected to a late inoculation. Prior to the inoculation, all trial plants were sampled by removing the terminal leaflet from the highest fully-developed leaf. Leaf material was tested by ELISA to ensure the absence of PepMV. Virus inoculum was prepared by grinding a few leaves of the infector plants in inoculation buffer (the Netherlands, Hungary and UK: PBS, pH 7.4; Spain: 0,01M PBS, pH 7.2 + 0.2% (p/w) DIECA + 0.2% (p/w) sodium bisulphite). Inoculations were conducted by rubbing sap extracts plus carborundum or Celite on the upper fully developed leaves when the plants were in the 5th truss-stage. Fera (UK) isolated RNA from leaves from infected tomato plants and subsequently confirmed that the PepMV present in the trial belonged to the European tomato strain (first season) and the Chile2 strain (second season).

Prior to the inoculation, sanitation methods were put in place to minimise the risk of early PepMV infection and of other pathogen infections. Once inoculations were done, all work in the compartment/area with healthy plants was carried out prior to the work in the compartment/area with infected plants to avoid the unwanted spread of PepMV. Both compartments/areas had their own stock of equipment, overalls, gloves, shoe covers and caps. Disinfection mats were placed in front of the entrance of both compartments/areas and were wetted regularly with disinfectant. The same instructed personal performed all labor throughout both growing seasons and no uninvited entry was allowed. All harvest from the trial was disposed in a safe way. As the same facilities were used during both growing seasons, all compartments and tunnels were thoroughly disinfected in between the two seasons. The watering and irrigation systems were also disinfected. All tools were either disinfected or replaced by new tools.

Site-specific trial design

Because the tomato growing seasons are not synchronic throughout the EU, tomato plants were sown, planted and inoculated at different times of the year to ensure that crop management was in line with the local commercial practice (Table 2). The type of greenhouse used at commercial facilities varies between the different partner countries (*Fig. 2*). As such, the trial lay out was designed to fit the local type of facilities. As an example the UK trial design is shown below (*Fig. 3*).

Figure 1. Local green- and glasshouse facilities in the (a.) UK, (b.), Spain, (c.) Hungary and (d.) the Netherlands as used during the PEPEIRA trials.

Table 2. Site-specific trial management in each participating EU-country.

Country	Growing season	Sowing	Transplantation	Inoculation	First harvest	Final harvest
UK	2007-2008	14 March 2008 ¹	15 May 2008	18 June 2008	9 July 2008	17 September 2008
	2008-2009	14 January 2009	5 March 2009	9 April 2009	20 May 2009	26 August 2009
Spain	2007-2008	21 August 2007	1 October 2007	20 November 2007	6 February 2008	28 May 2008
	2008-2009	22 September 2008	10 November 2008 ²	18 February 2009 ³	15 April 2009	1 July 2009
Hungary	2007	13 March 2007	20 April 2007	18/19 June 2007	4 July 2007	4 October 2007
	2008	15 March 2008	28 April 2008	20 June 2008	27 June 2008	24 September 2008
Netherlands	2007-2008	14 November 2007	8 January 2008	3 March 2008	9 April 2008	17 September 2008 ⁴
	2008-2009	21 November 2008	6 January 2009	11 March 2009	14 April 2009	27 October 2008

¹ Seed was originally sown late November 2007. However, just after planting on 11 January, Defra's Plant Health Division decided that the glasshouse facilities at STC needed to be upgraded to ensure that the virus could be contained and destroyed on site. This overruled the earlier approval of the trial set-up by the Plant Health Division and delayed the start of the trial by approximately 3 months.

² In the second Spanish growing season, sowing and transplantation dates were adapted to avoid problems with whitefly-transmitted viruses.

³ The inoculation date in the second Spanish growing season was also changed relative to the first season, because the cooler weather conditions of that winter slowed down plant development considerably

⁴ In 2009, yields decreased steadily towards the end of the season after the 19th week of harvesting. In 2008, production levels also decreased after the 19th week, but subsequently dropped sharply after the 23rd week and the trial was therefore stopped earlier in 2008.

UK-specific trial design

Plants in the UK were propagated and grown at Stockbridge Technology Centre (STC), North Yorkshire (Fig. 2a). The experimental layout is shown in Fig. 3. The glasshouse was split by treatment. The infected treatment consisted of four replicated plots on one side of the glasshouse, while the non-inoculated (healthy) plots were on the other side. Each experimental plot consisted of two rows, each row containing ten plants. Bell pepper is considered to be a non-host of PepMV and was planted between each plot to avoid the spread of PepMV by plant-to-plant contact.

Between sowing and planting, 200 plants were tested for the presence of PepMV by ELISA. On 13 May 2008 and 3 February 2009, 180 tomato plants (at the 5th true leaf stage) were sampled by removing the terminal leaflet from the highest fully-developed leaf. Similarly, the uppermost fully developed leaf of 20 bell pepper plants (barrier crop) was sampled and tested. Tomato seedlings were transplanted into single rock wool blocks that were subsequently placed on rock wool slabs. Plants were trained to a crop wire at circa 4 m height. In both growing seasons, the healthy control treatment and infected treatment were located in two separate areas of the same glasshouse compartment. Both areas were identical in size and had a cropping area of 90 m². Crop density was 2.2 tomato plants per m². Sanitation methods were put in place to minimise the risk of transmitting PepMV, and other pathogens. For example, entry of bumble bees and larger sized pests that may spread PepMV was avoided by screening the glasshouse vents. Plant pollination was done by hand.

Figure 3. Schematic map of the UK trial set-up. A double door entry system was present for both glasshouse sections. Each square represents a single plant of the tomato cv. Cedrico (healthy = green squares; PepMV-infected = red squares) or of the sweet pepper barrier crop (grey squares). Tomato stems were rotated clockwise within the replicate plots.

DAS-ELISA and PepMV concentration

Double sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbant assays (DAS-ELISA) was used to test whether all tomato plants were free of PepMV prior to the inoculation. During the trials, the healthy tomato plants were tested by DAS-ELISA to confirm the absence of PepMV on a weekly basis.

Every two (Hungary) or four weeks (other trial sites), four pooled samples of infected Cedrico plants were taken to determine the PepMV concentration. The terminal leaflet of the upper fully developed leaf was collected from three plants per plot and 10 ml of PBS-Tween buffer (pH 7.4) was added per gram of leaf tissue to allow grinding. Anti-PepMV rabbit polyclonal antiserum (Prime Diagnostics, The Netherlands) was diluted to 1:1,000 (v/v) and used according to the

appended specifications. Reactions were measured at 405 nm with an ELISA reader (Bio-Tek Elx808 or Multiskan RC). Samples were considered positive if absorbance levels exceeded background levels by a factor three. Viral load is either reported as (relative) absorbance values (Spain, UK, and Hungary) or as virus concentration (the Netherlands). To quantify viral concentration, a dilution series of known amounts of the 1066 isolate was assayed on each plate to establish a standard curve.

Flowering and fruit-set

Flowering and fruit-set were monitored on at least three plants per replicate plot, adding up to a total of 12 plants per treatment. Monitoring started on the first truss above the inoculated leaf and continued for the next five to seven trusses (the Netherlands: truss 5 to 11; UK: truss 5 to 11; Hungary: truss 5 to 9; Spain: truss 4 to 9). Flowering and fruit-set data were collected weekly.

Leaf symptom development

Symptoms were monitored weekly with a standardized scoring form on which plant heads and foliage were rated for the presence of virus-related symptoms. Rated symptoms as described by the monitoring protocol were leaf bubbling, mosaic and nettle heads (in plants heads), and yellow spots and scorching (foliage). The protocol allowed for additional symptoms to be monitored as well. Additionally observed and rated symptoms were leaf deformation (the Netherlands, UK) and necrosis on the petals (Spain, Hungary). All symptoms were scored on a 0 (no symptoms) to 4 (very severe) scale. Eight plants (Spain) or three plants (other sites) were visually assessed per replicate plot.

Shelf-life

Samples of healthy and PepMV-infected fruits were subjected to a shelf-life test at three times during both growing seasons (early, mid- en late-season) according to the prescribed trial protocol.

Harvesting

Tomato fruits were harvested weekly. Fruits were sorted into size classes, graded, counted and weighted on the day of harvest. Fruit quality assessments were based on Directive 790/2000 EC "Marketing standard for tomatoes". Fruits were assigned to the size categories <35 mm, 37-47 mm, 47-57 mm, 57-67 mm or >67 mm. All fruits were also graded as either Class I, Class II or waste, based on the presence of marbling, fruit discoloration, uneven ripening or other deviations, such as lack of firmness, cracks, blemishes, and blossom-end rot (Table 3; Fig. 4). Fruits that were smaller than 35 mm were always graded as waste.

Table 3. Definition of classes as described in the quality assessment protocol.

Class	Characteristics
Class I	Even colour (although does allow a slight defect in colouring) Firm No cracks or blemishes
Class II	Reasonably firm Small defects in colouring, e.g. mottling, uneven red colour Healed cracks less than 3 cm in length Minor blemishes
Waste (out grades)	Irregular colour severe uneven ripening, 'greenbacks' Over ripe (soft/rotting) Major defects e.g. bad bruising, blossom-end rot Open wounds/cuts Fruit smaller than 35 mm

Figure 4 Examples of fruits with colour defects. Fruits on the top left are still considered to be class I despite of the small colour defects. Fruits on the top right are downgraded to class II. The bottom row illustrates the difference between a class II (left and right) and a waste class fruit (middle).

Statistical analysis

An analysis of variance for repeated measures was done on fruit yield and quality data from season 2 (2008 for the Hungarian trial; 2009 for other countries). All analyses were carried out using Genstat release 10.2 (VSN International Ltd, UK). The first year trial data (2007 for the Hungarian trial; 2008 for other countries) were analysed using a REML linear mixed model for repeated measures approach because the data sets were unbalanced.

Results

DAS-ELISA and PepMV concentration

At all trial sites, tomato plants were free of PepMV at the start of the trials as determined by DAS-ELISA. At none of the trial sites, PepMV was detected in the healthy control plants at anytime. In those plants that were inoculated with either *1066* or *PCH-06/104*, PepMV could be detected by DAS-ELISA on the first day that the plants were tested. The first DAS-ELISA test took place 2-4 wpi in Hungary, UK and Spain. In the Dutch trials, PepMV was already detected in all inoculated plants at nine dpi.

The general pattern which arises from the tests on the PepMV concentration is that this concentration fluctuates somewhat throughout the season (*Figure 5*). It should be kept in mind that the growing seasons at the different sites are not synchronic, which may explain differences in these fluctuations. Local weather conditions may also affect the PepMV concentration. One notable exception to the moderate fluctuations is a sharp drop at the end of August in the Hungarian trial on *1066* (*Fig. 5c*), when temperatures in the greenhouse were very high. A second exception is the Dutch trial, in which the concentration of PepMV in the *PCH-06/104*-infected plants was initially much higher than the PepMV concentration in the *1066*-infected plants (*Figure 5a*), but then experienced a sharp drop to end up on a similar level as *1066* in June.

Figure 5. *PepMV* concentration throughout the growing season as measured by DAS-ELISA. (a.) *PepMV* concentration (\pm s.e.) in the Dutch trials. (b.) Relative absorbance values in the Spanish trial. Absorbance values at the first time point were set to 100%. (c.) Absorbance values of 1066-infected plants in the Hungarian trial. (d.) Absorbance values of PCH-06/104-infected plants in the Hungarian trial. (e.) Adjusted absorbance values of 1066-infected plants (relative to healthy control plants) in the UK trial. (f.) Adjusted absorbance values of PCH-06/104-infected plants (relative to healthy control plants) in the UK trial.

Flowering and fruit-set

1066 and PCH-06/104 had no effect on fruit set. A small tendency towards fewer flowers was observed after inoculation with both 1066 and PCH-06/104.

Symptom development

The mild PepMV isolate *1066* and the aggressive isolate *PCH-06/104* differed clearly from each other with regard to symptom development on leaves and sepals (*Fig. 6*). One should, however, keep in mind that both isolates were assessed in different growing seasons and the crops were consequently affected by different weather conditions. This may have influenced the symptom expression to some extent. Therefore, healthy tomato plants were assessed as well to provide a baseline figure.

Figure 6. Both (a. Hungary) 1066 and (b. the Netherlands) PCH-06/104 caused the typical PepMV symptom of yellow spots. PCH-06/104 also caused (c. the Netherlands) leaf bubbling and nettle heads, (d. Hungary) leaf deformation, and (e. Spain) necrosis on the sepals of the developed fruits below the 5th truss.

Table 4. *PepMV*-related symptoms observed in the greenhouse trials. The table displays the mean symptom score.

Treatment	Healthy (1 st season)	1066 (1 st season)	Healthy (2 nd season)	PCH-06/104 (2 nd season)
<u>Dutch trial</u>	(n=348)	(n=348)	(n=336)	(n=336)
<u>Plant heads/foilage</u>				
Leaf bubbling	0.08	0.22	0.11	0.90
Nettle heads	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.66
Discoloration/Mosaic	0.22	0.89	0.31	1.39
Yellow spots	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.90
Leaf deformation	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.24
<u>Spanish trial</u>	(n=544)	(n=544)	(n=384)	(n=384)
<u>Leaves</u>				
Leaf bubbling	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
Nettle Heads	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.2
Mosaic	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2
Yellow spots	0.0	0.0	0.01	0.2
Yellowing ¹	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.3
Purple appearance ¹	0.9	0.9	1.2	0.9
Necrotic reddening ¹	1.0	0.8	1.6	1.0
<u>Petals</u>				
Mosaic/necrotic spots	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.9
<u>Hungarian trial</u>	(n=168)	(n=168)	(n=168)	(n=168)
<u>Plant heads/foilage</u>				
Leaf bubbling	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
Yellow spots	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2
Scorching	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
<u>Petals</u>				
Necrosis	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9
<u>UK trial</u>	(n=132)	(n=132)	(n=168)	(n=168)
<u>Plant heads/foilage</u>				
Leaf bubbling	0.04	0.05	0.05	1.23
Nettle heads	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
Discoloration/Mosaic	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.38
Yellow spots	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
Leaf deformation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02

¹ These symptoms are probably caused by viruses other than PepMV

Effect of PepMV on yield

When the yield data for all four participating countries are analysed together, a number of factors need to be considered. First, the location of the trial had the largest influence on yield, whereby southern sites tended to produce less yield than northern sites. Second, sampling date had a large influence on yield. In general, yield increased shortly after sampling began, and then decreased. This was true for all countries except Spain, where yield tended to increase over the season. As there was no interaction between site and treatment in both the 2007/08 ($P=0.919$) and 2009 ($P=0.181$) seasons, overall conclusions can be made about the effects of PepMV isolate *1066* and *PCH-06/104* on tomato yield across all sites. With this in mind, PepMV isolate *1066* had no measurable effect on total yield of Class I, Class II and waste together. However, isolate *PCH-06/104* reduced the total yield of Class I, Class II and waste together by 4.24%.

Despite each trial site showing similar effects in terms of the impact of PepMV on yield, it is worth considering the results from each country separately. In each of the individual trials carried out in the first year of the project (i.e. in Hungary, Spain, the Netherlands and UK) isolate *1066* had no significant effect on total yield at any location. Also, in all countries, the number of harvested fruits was not affected by the virus. *PCH-06/104* had no effect on total yield (g/plant/week) at any of the four individual trial locations except Spain where yield was reduced by 10%. However, there was a tendency towards lower total yield in the *PCH-06/104*-infected plants in the Hungarian and UK trials compared to healthy plants.

Figure 7. Marbling (upper left) and uneven ripening (upper right) caused by the *PCH-06/104* isolate in the Hungarian trial. Uneven ripening (bottom left and right) also occurred on the first four trusses of plants infected with the isolate *PCH-06/104* in the Dutch trial.

Effect of PepMV on fruit quality

Clear differences could be observed between the PepMV isolates *1066* and *PCH-06/104* with regard to the occurrence of fruit symptoms. PepMV isolate *1066* had very little effect on fruit quality in the trials. Typical PepMV-related symptoms (i.e. fruit marbling and uneven ripening, Figure 7) were observed at all four trial sites, but their occurrence in infected plots did not differ statistically with fruit symptoms in uninfected plots..

PCH-06/104 had a large effect on fruit quality. In Hungary, the first fruit symptoms (i.e. marbling) appeared shortly after inoculation (Figure 7) and were observed throughout the whole trial.

Necrosis was observed on the petals of some fruits. In the Dutch trial, especially the first four trusses displayed clear PepMV related symptoms (uneven ripening, Figure 7). These trusses were already developing at the time of the inoculation. Similarly, in the UK trial, marbling on fruit was seen within four weeks after inoculation in plants infected with *PCH-06/104*.

Overall, isolate *PCH-06/104* reduced the yield of Class I fruit in the first seven weeks of harvests. This represents a drop in yield of Class I fruit of 23%. Consequently, there was a 60% increase in Class II fruit in the same period. In weeks 8 to 14, there was no effect of virus on fruit quality.

In the 2007/08 (*1066*) trials, Class I yields were higher in the beginning of the season than later in the season. Isolate *1066* did not affect the yield of Class I, Class II or waste compared with non-infected control plants.

Table 5a. Effect of PepMV isolate *1066* on yield of tomato (g/plant/week) over a 14 week harvest period. Values in brackets are changes in yield within each class category as a result of PepMV infection (% yield compared with healthy control plots). A minus value represents a yield reduction due to virus infection. * and ** represent significant yield effects at $P<0.05$ and $P<0.01$ respectively.

Country	Class I		Class II		Waste	
	Healthy	Inoculated	Healthy	Inoculated	Healthy	Inoculated
Hungary	165.2	144.7 (-12.4%)	59.4	60.4 (1.6%)	47.2	69.2 (46.4%)**
Netherlands	661.4	642.9 (-2.8%)	57.2	61.9 (8.2%)	2.1	3.1 (47.1%)
Spain	17.1	25.9 (50.8%)	134.1	144.2 (7.5%)	215.3	204.4 (-5.1%)
UK	580.6	567.7 (-2.2%)	55.2	90.7 (64.6%)*	4.3	3.8 (-10.7%)
Country Mean	266.6	256.1 (-4.0%)	83.2	96.0 (15.4%)	88.5	91.3 (3.2%)

Table 5b. Effect of PepMV isolate *PCH-06/104* on yield of tomato (g/plant/week) over a 14-week harvest period². Values in brackets are changes in yield within each class category as a result of PepMV infection (% yield compared with healthy control plots). A minus value represents a yield reduction due to virus infection. *, ** and *** represent significant yield effects at $P<0.05$, $P<0.01$, and $P<0.001$ respectively.

Country	Class I		Class II		Waste	
	Healthy	Inoculated	Healthy	Inoculated	Healthy	Inoculated
Hungary	218.0	153.7 (-29.5%)**	84.7	118.3 (39.7%)**	48.6	62 (27.6%)
Netherlands	642.7	558.3 (-13.1%)***	87.6	167.1 (90.7%)***	21.4	34.4 (60.7%)
Spain	63.5	48.7 (-23.3%)	161.6	123.8 (-23.4%)**	280.0	277.2 (-1.0%)
UK	593.6	530.3 (-10.4%)**	60.1	93.9 (56.2%)**	37.5	37.8 (0.8%)
Country Mean	376.2	320.4 (-14.8%)***	98.3	123.9 (26.0%)***	96.9	102.8 (6.1%)

² The means presented in the analysis of variance are calculated after estimating the values for the weeks, treatments, countries and replicate blocks when data were missing. As a result of this, the predicted means will therefore not match the observed means exactly for the treatments for each country where missing values were present (and in the case of the Netherlands, data were collected beyond 14 weeks).

Conclusions

Replicated semi commercial-scale trials were carried out over two consecutive seasons in four major tomato producing areas throughout Europe (i.e. Hungary, the Netherlands, Spain and UK) to assess the economic effect of PepMV under different environmental and cropping conditions. A mild isolate, 1066, had no effect on total fruit yield or yield of Class I, Class II or waste fruit over a 14 week production. *PCH-06/104*, selected as an aggressive PepMV isolate, reduced the yield of Class I fruit by around 14% over a 15-week period ($P < 0.001$). This isolate also reduced total fruit yield by just over 4% ($P = 0.057$). The effect of isolate *PCH-06/104* on Class I and total yield reduction tended to be greater during the earlier part of the season.

There were differences in fruit yields between countries. In general, the trials in the southern European sites produced lower yield than those in the northern countries. Despite these differences, the effects of the aggressive isolate, *PCH-06/104*, on Class I fruit yield was consistent: yields were reduced by between 10 and 29%. The effects of *PCH-06/104* on total fruit yield was less consistent: yields were reduced by between 4 and 11% in three out of four countries. In one country, the Netherlands, total yield was unaffected by *PCH-06/104*. All results are summarized in table 6.

Table 6. Summary of the effects of the PepMV isolates *1066* and *PCH-06/104* on tomato plants grown under conditions similar to the commercial practice in the UK, Hungary, Spain and the Netherlands.

Effect on:	Isolate	<i>1066</i> (mild isolate)				<i>PCH-06/104</i> (aggressive isolate)			
	Country	UK	Hungary	Spain	Netherlands	UK	Hungary	Spain	Netherlands
Fruit set		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>
Symptoms in plant heads and foliage		Mild symptoms: Yellow spots	Mild symptoms: Yellow spots	Mild symptoms: One plant with yellow spots, necrosis on petals	Mild symptoms: Yellow spots and discoloration	leaf bubbling, mild mosaic	leaf bubbling, scorch, yellow spots	Mild symptoms: yellow spots, necrosis on petals	Clear symptoms shortly after inoculation, mild symptoms later on
Total yield - weight		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	10% reduction	<i>No effect</i>
Total yield - No. of fruits		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>
Fruit size distribution		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	Slightly larger fruits	<i>No effect</i>	<i>Smaller fruits early season</i>	smaller fruits	No general effect on size	<i>No effect</i>
Fruit quality (% downgrading from Class I to Class II)		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	10%	29%	23%	13%
Fruit symptoms		<i>No effect</i>	Uneven ripening observed, but not PepMV related	<i>No effect</i>	Uneven ripening observed, but not PepMV related	Marbling and uneven ripening	Marbling and uneven ripening observed	<i>No effect</i>	Increased occurrence of uneven ripening
Shelf-life		<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	<i>No effect</i>	Small negative effect early in the season

Economic model

General description of the model

An economic model was constructed that calculates the effect of the presence of PepMV on producers and consumers at a country level. Estimates of aggregate disease costs can be used for assigning research resources or to evaluate control measures. Most diseases cause production losses (direct losses – yield), but others affect quality and marketability as is the case here (direct losses – downgrading). The method is a much simplified version of that used by Brennan et al (2004) in the assessment of the economic impact of karnal bunt.

Basis of the model

The data requirements for the calculation of yield and quality losses are interrelated and consist of area, yield, production and price data. For area, yield and production data (FAO, 2007) was used, but this does lead to some inconsistent results and therefore the FAO data should be crosschecked with country specific data if available.

Re-classifying tomatoes from one type to another is equivalent to a shift of the supply curve for each type. The economic effects of such a change are measured as changes in the “Producer surplus” and the “Consumer surplus”, which are measures of the economic welfare of each of the two groups. Changing fresh tomato produce to use in the processing sector is equivalent to a shift of the supply curve for each tomato market in the affected region:

- A shift to the left in the supply curve for fresh tomatoes, as quantities are taken out of the fresh market
- A shift to the right in the supply curve for processed tomatoes, as downgraded fresh tomatoes are added to the processed market

The model estimates the difference in producer and consumer surpluses in the presence of PepMV and the surpluses that would apply in its absence. The net welfare benefits depend on the net effect of producer and consumer surpluses in each of the fresh and processing tomato markets. Figure 7 presents this graphically.

The economic welfare analysis undertaken through shifts in supply and demand curves should incorporate all of the components of disease impacts, reactions and control costs that affect the quantity of tomatoes available within each class. The welfare effects include the economic impacts of (a) yield losses, (b) destruction of growing crops, (c) destruction of harvested product (if applicable), (d) downgrading, (e) export bans (if any) and (f) price effects. Some of these components [(a) to (d)] can be estimated directly. Control costs have not been estimated due to limitations of time and data. However, the economic losses estimated by the model represent a threshold in terms of how much can be justified to be spent on control. This will depend on the efficacy of control in terms of its impact on the degree and rate of spread.

Cost Benefit Analysis (using UK data)

If 10% of UK tomato crops became infected by an aggressive isolate of PepMV, the economic losses would be around US\$1,344,000 (or 1.1% of total revenue) for direct yield losses, and nearly US\$612,000 (or 0.5% of revenue) for downgrading losses (Figure 18). This assumes no markets for Class II and waste fruit. If there is a market for Class II fruit, the losses due to PepMV infection changes to US\$1,039,000 (or 0.8% of revenue) due to yield loss, and US\$306,000 (or 0.2% of revenue) due to downgrading losses. It is highly likely that disease incidence levels could reach over 10% of crops if no action was taken to prevent entry of PepMV into EU countries. Also, more aggressive isolates of Chile 2 are becoming the predominant isolates in European tomato crops. There are a limited number of options when considering how to deal with a PepMV outbreak. Option 1 is to do nothing. This would result in an estimated loss in revenue of 1.2% (if a secondary market exists for Class II fruit) and 1.6% (if no secondary market exists for Class II fruit) if crops are infected with an aggressive isolate. The second option is to remove all plants in an outbreak site,

decontaminate the glasshouse and replant. At present, this is the only intervention available to tomato growers in EU Member States to control a PepMV outbreak. A conservative estimate of the cost of removing and replacing tomato plants in GB (assuming 10% of sites are contaminated) would be US\$1,943,000. This assumes that the cost of removal (i.e. cost of planting material, growing medium, labour, removal of materials) is US\$10.37/m² (M Schenk, Wageningen UR, pers. comm). This is likely to be an underestimate of the true cost of removal and replanting because this figure does not take into account any reduction in the length of harvest period.

The replanting cost is approximately 99% of the the economic loss due to yield reduction and downgrading where there is no secondary market for Class II fruit (US\$2,753,000) and 1.45 times the economic loss due to yield loss and downgrading where there is a market for Class II fruit (US\$1,735,000). The relative values remain the same irrespective of the number of sites affected.

Therefore, the cost of replacing crops at outbreak sites is, at best, equivalent to the estimated financial loss due to infection with an aggressive isolate of PepMV.

Ultimately, the benefit to the industry of preventing PepMV from entry into each member state is likely to be in the order of 1% of total annual revenue.

UK	Weeks 20 to 33	Processing sector	n							
Box 1: No PepMV										
Production	Area (Ha)	Yield (t/Ha)	Grade I (%)	Grade II (%)	Waste %	Grade I	Grade II	Price I	50%	Revenue I
Tomatoes	213	401.9	86%	9%	5%	42,336	4,286	\$ 1,605.35	\$ -	\$ 67,963,510.29
	Fresh	Peeled								
Imports	209,822	180,963								
Exports	2,298	1,246								
Consumption	249,860	179,717								
	Fresh	Peeled	Total							
Producer surplus	\$61,167,159	\$0	\$61,167,159	PS based on domestic production						
Consumer surplus	\$334,260,136	\$0	\$334,260,136	CS based on domestic consumption i.e. includes imported						
Box 2: with PepMV										
	Area infected	10%								
Production	Area (Ha)	Yield (t/Ha)	Grade I (%)	Grade II (%)	Waste %	Grade I	Grade II	Price I	Price II	Revenue
Fresh	213	384.9	80%	14%	6%	41,884	4,527	\$1,608.98	\$0.00	\$67,390,627
	Fresh	Peeled								
Imports	209,822	180,963								
Exports	2,298	1,246								
Consumption	249,408	FALSE								
	Fresh	Peeled	Total							
Producer surplus	\$60,651,564	\$0	\$60,651,564							
Consumer surplus	\$333,204,034	\$0	\$333,204,034							
Box 3: Direct losses										
		Value (%)								
Yield loss	-\$724,746	-1.1								
Downgrading loss	-\$386,989	-0.6								

Figure 8. Economic cost to the UK tomato industry of 10% of crops being infected by an aggressive isolate of PepMV

Table 7: Deliverables List WP2

List all deliverables, giving date of submission and any proposed revision to plans.

Del. no.	Deliverable name	Work package no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Estimated indicative person-months	Used indicative person-months *)	Lead contractor
2.1	Completed glasshouse trials over two seasons on four different locations	2	M34	M34	20		2
2.2	Assessment of impact of PepMV on infected tomato crops	2	M34	M34	17		2
2.3	Econometric model for assessing economic impact	2	M36	M36	6		2
2.4	Cost benefit analysis of PepMV control measures	2	M36	M36	6		2

*) if available

Table 8: Milestones List WP2

List all milestones, giving date of achievement and any proposed revision to plans.

Milestone no.	Milestone name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Lead contractor
2.1	Meeting (month 4) to standardise recording and trial design at all sites	2	M4	M6	2
2.2	Completion of year 1-2 trials at sites in Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain and UK	2	M34	M34	2
2.3	Completion of year 2-3 trials at sites in Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain and UK	2	M36	M36	2
2.4	Statistical analysis and econometric modelling of trial data	2	M36	M36	2

All WP 2 deliverables and milestones have been met.

WP 3: PepMV characteristics and occurrence

Deliverables

- 3.1 A report on the most important biological and genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains present in the different EU member states.
- 3.2 An evaluation of methods to accurately detect and diagnose all relevant PepMV strains and isolates.
- 3.3 A report on the occurrence and spread of the different PepMV isolates and strains over the different EU member states.
- 3.4 An evaluation of the possible risks of PepMV strains and variants on tomato and other Solanaceous crops.
- 3.5 An evaluation of the possible risk of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV within the EU.

One of the main objectives of WP3 was to determine the occurrence and spread of different isolates and strains of PepMV present in the different member states as well as their main biological and molecular characteristics, with the aim to develop and evaluate methods to accurately detect and diagnose all relevant PepMV strains and isolates. The other main objective was to evaluate the possible risks of PepMV for tomato (including the risk for seed transmission in this crop) and other economically important Solanaceous crops like pepper, potato, aubergine and tobacco.

Basically all partners contributed to the deliverables in this WP by participating in one or more of the different studies carried out.

Since the first occurrence of PepMV in the EU several partners, since 2007 cooperating within the Pepeira consortium collected biological and genetic datasets of isolates and strains of PepMV. Additional information is available in the international literature and databases. All datasets were compiled and from their comparisons relevant biological and genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains present in the EU member states were determined and missing information was identified. PCR-based methods were developed that allow both sensitive virus detection as well as distinction between different virus strains and isolates. Relevant and characteristic PepMV isolates and strains were preserved in a plant virus collection at PRI. This will ensure their future availability to science and industry for isolate and type virus comparisons both at the molecular and biological level, allow validation of diagnostics as well as durable plant resistance if it would become available through the breeding industry

The field trials in WP2 provided detailed information on the biological characteristics of PepMV type isolates on a single classic type tomato of a variety widely grown within the EU. In a 'ring test' set-up, carried out over a two-year period, different tomato varieties as well as a selected set of indicator plants were mechanically inoculated with three type isolates of the most important strains of PepMV. In addition four agronomical important Solanaceous crop plants i.e. tobacco, potato, eggplant and pepper were also mechanically inoculated. These experiments provided information on the effects of local conditions and varieties on PepMV symptoms and their development during the growing season as well as on the potential risk new strains of the virus poses for these important crops widely grown in the different EU member states.

From available and developed serological and molecular diagnostics a selection was evaluated for sensitivity and specificity. Selected diagnostics were then further evaluated in ring tests by all consortium partners for their ability to accurately detect and diagnose all currently known PepMV strains. The results from this ring test were used to develop an EPPO protocol in WP4

Mechanical transmission of PepMV is the main means of spread of the virus within and between countries. Virus transmission through infected seeds remains a point of discussion. Selected partners will therefore test levels of possible virus transmission through seed obtained from the plant mechanically inoculated with selected PepMV isolates.

Biological and genetic characteristics of PepMV

Deliverables 3.1 and 3.4

Deliverable 3.1: A report on the most important biological and genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains present in the different EU member states.

Deliverable 3.4: An evaluation of the possible risks of PepMV strains and variants on tomato and other Solanaceous crops.

Both deliverables are connected in their evaluation of the biological characteristics of the different PepMV strains and the possible risks these may pose for tomato and other Solanaceous crops. Combined results of the work on both deliverables are therefore presented her. More detailed information can be obtained from the second and third year project reports.

Biological characteristics of PepMV

There are now four main strains recognized of PepMV;

- Pepino (or Peru) strain
- EU-tomato strain
- Chile-2 strain
- US1 strain

The pepino strain is the type strain of PepMV as first described by Jones *et al* in 1980. It is very similar to the EU-tomato strain with over 95% sequence identity. So far it has only a very limited distribution. The EU-tomato strain was the first PepMV to be discovered in Europe (van der Vlugt *et al*, 2000) and is now distributed worldwide. Its effects on tomato are generally relatively mild but isolates causing severe symptoms have been reported. Since 2006 the Chile-2 strain of PepMV (Ch2) has spread very quickly over Europe and the rest of the world. It is now widely distributed. Of both strains, weak isolates (i.e. causing very mild symptoms) and aggressive isolates (i.e. causing very distinct and detrimental symptoms) have been reported. Isolates of both the EU-tomato strain and the Ch2-strain can (and do) occur in mixed infection. Genetic recombinants between these two strains have been observed as a result of these mixed infections. In addition since 'weak' or 'aggressive' isolates can not yet be recognized by a specific test, mixed infections can have unpredictable effects on tomato crops.

The fourth PepMV strain recognized is US1. First reported only in the USA (Maroon-Lango, 2005) it has now been found in Spain (Alfaro-Fernandez *et al.*, Plant disease 92:1590, 2008) and as such there is a serious risk it may spread further across Europe. Apart from its sequence, very little is known about this strain. Following the first introduction into Europe there is a risk for further introductions and spread of US1. In this respect it is important to have more information on the characteristics of this PepMV strain. Therefore it was decided to include this strain in the work in WP3 on PepMV characteristics and occurrence.

The following partners took part in the work on biological characterization of the genotypes:

Partner 1	PRI	The Netherlands
Partner 2	FERA	UK
Partner 4	UPV	Spain
Partner 5	CsM-MgSzH	Hungary
Partner 6	AU	Denmark
Partner 8	CRA	Italy
Partner 11	NIB	Slovenia
Partner 14	IOR	Poland
Partner 15	BPI	Greece
Partner 16	BioForsk	Norway
Partner 17	PPI	Bulgaria

Summary

The development of symptoms and infection rates in local cultivars of important Solanaceous food plants and indicator plants were assayed at different European geographic localities for three isolates of *Pepino mosaic virus* (PepMV) belonging to the European tomato (1066), the Chili2 (PCH06/104) and the US1 genotype. Presence of virus was tested by DAS ELISA. Sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) and potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) developed in general no symptoms when inoculated with the three genotypes, and leaves and roots were most often ELISA negative. A local PepMV isolate included by one partner gave systemic mosaic in one potato variety. Eggplant (*S. melongena*), tomato (*S. lycopersicum*) and tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) nearly always showed symptoms and were ELISA positive in both leaves and roots. *S. melongena* thus is a possible overseen, but very susceptible host for PepMV and the possible role as infection source in the industry must be considered.

N. occidentalis 37B, *N. tabacum* 'Xanthi', *N. rustica*, *N. glutinosa*, *N. benthamiana* and *Chenopodium quinoa* were tested as indicator plants. *N. benthamiana* showed to be good for isolation and propagation of PepMV. *N. occidentalis* 37B are useful both for isolation, propagation and differentiation of isolates, and *N. tabacum* 'Xanthi', *N. rustica*, *N. glutinosa* showed to be useful for differentiating the three genotypes based on symptom development.

In general bigger differences in symptom development between the three PepMV genotypes in the same plant cultivar could be observed than differences between cultivars infected with the same genotype.

Only few cases of possible influence of the geographic locality on the specific trials were recorded, as for example no symptom development in tomato cultivars in the Polish trials.

Methods used and Results obtained

At least five plants of the different plant species and cultivars were inoculated with the genotypes used. The inoculated plants were observed for symptom development regularly and kept for at least three weeks. The inoculated plants were in several cases back inoculated to a suitable test plants or checked for infection by ELISA or RT-PCR.

The selected PepMV genotypes were distributed by Partner 1 to the partners involved as freeze dried leaf material. These inoculums were propagated in *Nicotiana benthamiana* before they were used for further inoculation experiments.

In addition, local PepMV isolates were studied by some of the partners alongside the three chosen genotypes.

The results from these experiments are summarized below. More details can be found in the second and third year reports.

Capsicum annuum (sweet pepper)

Altogether 5 partners have done inoculation experiments with different cultivars of sweet pepper. The cultivar 'Bell Boy' was used by all partners. In addition 15 other, local cultivars were used by the different partners. In general, there were no symptoms observed except for the isolate US1 that gave systemic necrotic lesions in 3 out of 20 trials. ELISA results showed that the isolate 1066 were present in inoculated leaves in 4 out of 20 trials, the isolate PCH06/104 was present in inoculated leaves in 3 out of 20 trials, and the isolate US1 was present in inoculated leaves in 5 out of 20 trials. Altogether 9 out of these 10 ELISA positives were a documentation of latent, local infection.

From our study we can conclude that sweet pepper can occasionally be locally infected but is not a systemic host for the three isolates used in this study. It is likely that sweet pepper does not represent an important host in the epidemiology of PepMV.

Solanum tuberosum (potato)

As potato is in the same plant family as tomato and pepino, there has been an interest in the possibility of PepMV infecting this important crop from when the virus was first described (Jones et al. 1980). Jones et al.(1980) found several cultivars to be symptomlessly infected, except two

that showed severe systemic necrotic symptoms. Martin & Mousserion (2002) inoculated seven potato cultivars and found that two of them were sensitive ('Roseval' and 'Charlotte'), three resistant and two partly resistant.

In our study, the three selected genotypes were inoculated to altogether 16 potato cultivars. Necrotic local lesions were induced by the isolates 1066 and PCH06/104 in 3 out of 18 trials while systemic mosaic was induced by PCH06 in 1 out of 18 trials.

ELISA results from testing of leaves gave the following results. Isolate 1066 had developed a local infection in the leaves of 8 potato cultivars (Bintje, Mette, Beate, Juno, Riviera, Concord, Natasha, Jelly and Dali). Systemic infection in new leaves was found in 1 of 5 plants of cv. Beate (tested 33 days after inoculation), in 1 of 5 plants of each of the cultivars Riviera and Concorde, and in Natasha, Jelly and Dali. Isolate PCH06/104 had developed a local infection in the leaves of 7 potato cultivars (Bintje, Hamlet, Mette, Beate, Juno, Jelly and Dali). Systemic infection in new leaves was found in 2 of 5 plants of cv. Beate (tested 33 days after inoculation, and in cvs. Jelly and Dali. Isolate US1 had developed a local infection in the leaves of 6 potato cultivars (Bintje, Hamlet, Mette, Beate, Juno, Natascha) . Systemic infection in new leaves was only found in 1 of 5 plants of cv. Beate (tested 33 days after inoculation), and in cv. Natasha.

Elisa testing of roots gave 0 out of 7 trials, and ELISA testing of tubers gave 0 out of 3 trials. Planting of tubers harvested from inoculated plants did not result in secondary infected plants. Of the 16 cultivars tested 6 developed systemic infections in some plants, whereas 10 did not develop systemic infection when inoculated with the three selected isolates.

Partner 16 Bioforsk included the Norwegian isolate TomA2001-1 in this study. This isolate gave systemic infection in five out of five plants of the cultivar 'Beate', but did not infect 'Bintje' or 'Juno'. All plants of 'Beate' showed mosaic symptoms. PepMV in these symptomatic plants was confirmed by ELISA. Harvested tubers from these plants were stored and set for growing six months later. We then observed the same symptoms and could confirm the infection by ELISA, PCR and electron microscopy in these plants. This does indicate transmission of the TomA2001-1 isolate of PepMV through tubers of potato 'Beate'. See symptoms in figure below.

We can conclude that potato, in general, is not readily infected by the most common isolates of PepMV occurring in Europe. But the results from 'Beate' inoculated with the isolate TomA2001-1 shows that a systemic infection and transmission through the tubers can occur when the right isolates are combined with a sensitive cultivar.

Fig 8a. Potato 'Beate' with systemic mosaic associated with PepMV infection caused by isolate TomA2001-1. This plant was grown in Jan 2010 from tuber harvested from inoculation experiment in summer 2009.

Fig 8b. Non-inoculated control plant of potato 'Beate' grown in Jan 2010 from tuber harvested from inoculation experiment in summer 2009.

***Solanum melongena* (egg plant)**

Eggplant (*S. melongena*) is an important crop in the family *Solanaceae*. Altogether 7 cultivars were inoculated with the three PepMV genotypes. We observed mostly no local symptoms, but in 9 out of 45 trials some necrotic lesions were found, but systemic symptoms were observed in 19 out of 45 trials. ELISA testing confirmed leaf infection in all trials except for isolate US1 in 4 varieties. ELISA testing of roots confirmed infection in all except for isolate US1 in 3 varieties.

We can conclude that eggplant is a host for all isolates of PepMV tested, that also often shows systemic symptoms. This crop plant is susceptible to PepMV and may have a role in the epidemiology of PepMV.

***Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato)**

Symptoms of tomato have been studied by several groups and a wide range of symptoms have been described (Hanssen & Thomma 2009).

Altogether we inoculated 13 cultivars of tomato. ‘Moneymaker’ was used by all partners to have a common reference variety. We found no local symptoms in 10 out of 14 trials, but systemic symptoms in 13 out of 14 trials, except for one partner where no systemic symptoms were found. ELISA results confirmed that all leaves and roots were infected with PepMV in all varieties and trials.

All the three isolates chosen for this study gave relatively weak symptoms in tomato, but a local isolate (PepMV-Pa) included in the comparison in Polen gave pronounced necrotic symptoms in tomato. Similar differences in severity of symptoms in tomato between isolates has been repeatedly reported. This illustrates the great variation among PepMV isolates.

We may conclude that tomato is readily infected with all three genotypes, but the three genotypes did not give severe symptoms in our experiments. But a Polish isolate used by the Polish partner gave severe necrotic symptoms.

Fig 9a. Tomato Moneymaker new leaf with systemic infection 19 dpi, isolate 1066

Fig 9b. Tomato Moneymaker new leaf with systemic infection 19 dpi, isolate PCH06/104

Fig 9c. Tomato Moneymaker new leaf with systemic infection 19 dpi, isolate US1

Fig 9d. Tomato Moneymaker new leaf 19 dpi, healthy control

Photos: Dag-Ragnar Blystad

Fig 9e. Tomato Moneymaker new leaf with systemic necrotic symptoms, infected by isolate PepMV-Pa from Poland
Photo: Henryk Pospieszny

Nicotiana spp (Tobacco)

The use of test plants, especially different *Nicotiana* species, is important for isolating virus, propagating virus and for the differentiation of isolates. It is important to realize that symptoms may vary to a great extent according to growth conditions and genetic variability of the test plants. Different *Nicotiana* spp were tested with the PepMV isolates used earlier. Detailed results are described in the second third year reports.

Main conclusions

Pepper:

Although PepMV may cause a local infection in inoculated leaves in some pepper cultivars, sweet pepper is not a systemic host for the three isolates used in this study. It is likely that sweet pepper does not represent an important host in the epidemiology of PepMV.

Potato:

Although PepMV may cause some local and systemic infections, potato is not readily infected by the most common isolates of PepMV occurring in Europe. However the results from cultivar 'Beate' inoculated with the isolate TomA2001-1 show that a systemic infection can occur when the right isolate are combined with a sensitive cultivar. This is also in accordance with results from elsewhere. Potato therefore does not appear to be an important host in the epidemiology of PepMV.

Eggplant (Aubergine):

Eggplant is clearly a host for PepMV that also often shows systemic symptoms. This crop plant may have a role in the epidemiology of PepMV.

Tomato: Completely in line with many different observations tomato is readily infected with all three genotypes. The three genotypes did not give severe symptoms in our experiments but symptoms in tomato by different isolates of PepMV may be vary variable. There appears to be no correlation between symptom severity in tomato and virus genotype.

Tobacco:

- N. occidentalis* 37B: This test plant gives clear symptoms and can be used to differentiate isolates
- N. benthamiana* A sensitive test plant that is very useful for propagating virus, but is not so well suited for differentiation of isolates
- N. rustica*, *N. glutinosa*, *N. tabacum* 'Xanthi'
These test plant do not show a rapid response like *N. occidentalis* 37B and *N. benthamiana*, but are well suited for differentiation of isolates
- Chenopodium quinoa* This test plant is not regarded as important for PepMV, but our results indicate that it can be used for differentiation of isolates

Genetic characteristics of PepMV

Next to serological methods, molecular based methods (i.e. RT-PCR, TaqMan) are important tools for the detection of PepMV. Different primer pairs have been published and many more have been developed but remained unpublished. With the spread of the Chile 2 strain and possibly the new US1 strain, there is not only a need to detect all strain accurately but also to distinguish them. This implicates the need for the genetic characterisation of the different strains to allow detailed comparisons and '*in-silico*' development of PCR primer sets that should detect all strains of the virus.

Full and partial sequences of different PepMV isolates were determined from local PepMV isolates by the partners involved in the Pepeira project. An overview of these sequences is listed in the table below. In addition other PepMV sequences were collected from databases. '*In-silico*' analyses were performed on all these sequences to assess sequence variability between strains and within isolates from one strain. On the basis of these analyses candidate primer pairs were selected for further evaluation.

All comparisons show an identical genome organisation for all PepMV isolates from all different strains. (see figure 10). This organisation is typical for the potexviruses.

Figure 10. Schematic organization of the RNA genome of Pepino mosaic virus with its five open reading frames (ORFs). M7G = 5' cap, AAAAA_n = poly-A tail.

The overall conclusion from these detailed studies on the genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains is that the overall differences between isolates of one strain are very small (<5%). Differences between the different strains are much more pronounced (depending on the region under analysis up to around 20%) and these differences do offer opportunities for development of strain-specific PCR tests. No clear indicators could be identified in the sequences that may relate to differences in symptoms severity between isolates.

At the same time there are also regions of significant homology between the different strains which can be used for the development of molecular tests that should detect all isolates of the different PepMV strains.

The knowledge developed within this particular deliverable was used in the further development of reliable and accurate detection methods; deliverable 3.2.

Table 1 Overview of analyzed PepMV isolates

Isolate name	Strain	Full seq avail?	Acc. Number	Partial seq avail?	Acc. Number	Genomic region				
						ORF1	ORF2	ORF3	ORF4	ORF5
PepMV-Can 1	US1	No	-	YES	EU797176 EU791618 EU797177	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	 partial complete	 complete partial
4988	EU	No	-	YES	FJ384784	partial	complete	complete	complete	complete
Mu 98.1	EU	No	-		AM042564 AM113787 AM041929	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 00.1	EU	No	-	YES	AM042565 AM113788 AM041930	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 00.2	EU	No	-	YES	AM042566 AM113789 AM041931	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 00.3	EU	No	-	YES	AM042567 AM113790 AM041932	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 00.4	EU	No	-	YES	AM042588 AM113791 AM041933	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 00.5	EU	No	-	YES	AM042568 AM113792 AM041934	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial

Isolate name	Strain	Full seq avail?	Acc. Number	Partial seq avail?	Acc. Number	Genomic region				
						ORF1	ORF2	ORF3	ORF4	ORF5
					AM042590 AM040188 AM041935	partial partial	partial complete	partial complete	complete complete	partial partial
CI 01.1	EU	No	-	YES	AM113805 AM042569 AM041947	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
CI01.2	EU	No	-	YES	AM113806 AM042570 AM041948	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
CI 01.03	EU+PE	No	-	YES	AM042571 AM113807 AM040190 AM041949	partial partial	partial complete	 partial complete	partial complete complete	complete partial partial
Am 01.3	EU	No	-	YES	AM042572 AM113808 AM041950	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial
Mu 01.10	EU	No	-	YES	AM042575 AM113809 AM041951	partial partial	partial complete	 complete	partial complete	complete partial

Isolate name	Strain	Full seq avail?	Acc. Number	Partial seq avail?	Acc. Number	Genomic region				
						ORF1	ORF2	ORF3	ORF4	ORF5
AI 01.1	EU	No	-	YES	AM113810				partial	complete
					AM042573	partial	partial			
					AM041952	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
					AM042574	partial	partial			
					AM041953	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
AI 01.3	EU	No	-	YES	AM113812				partial	complete
					AM042576	partial	partial			
					AM041954	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
Ba 03.1	EU	No	-	YES	AM113828				partial	complete
					AM042578	partial	partial			
					AM041969	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
Mu 03.15	EU	No	-	YES	AM113827				partial	complete
					AM042577	partial	partial			
					AM041970	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
Mu 04.19	EU+PE	No	-	YES	AM113849				partial	complete
					AM042589	partial	partial			
					AM041991	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
					AM040189			partial	complete	partial
					AM041992	partial	complete	complete	complete	partial
					AM042579	partial	partial			

Isolate name	Strain	Full seq avail?	Acc. Number	Partial seq avail?	Acc. Number	Genomic region				
						ORF1	ORF2	ORF3	ORF4	ORF5
Mu04.15	CH2+EU	No		YES	AM040191 AM042591 AM041987 AM113845	partial	partial complete	complete	complete	complete
PMU06/26	CH2	No		YES	FJ263348		complete	complete	complete	complete
PMU08/44	CH2	No		YES	FJ263362		complete	complete	complete	complete
PepMV-H	EU-tomato	Yes	AM491606							
T 710-Roggero	CH2	Yes	to be submitted							
Sar/09	CH2	Yes	to be submitted							
Sic/ 24	CH2	Yes	to be submitted							
Sic/23	CH2	Yes	to be submitted							
French Isolate	European	Yes	AJ438767	N						
PCH 06/104	CH2	Yes	EF457097							
2206	CH2	Yes	EF599605							
1906	CH2	Yes	FJ457096							
1806	EU	Yes	EF457098							
Parekklesia	CH2	Yes	Not yet public							
Odou	CH2	Yes	Not yet public							

Isolate name	Strain	Full seq avail?	Acc. Number	Partial seq avail?	Acc. Number	Genomic region				
						ORF1	ORF2	ORF3	ORF4	ORF5
PepMV-PK	CH2	Yes	EF408821.3			X	X	X	X	X
PepMV-Pa	CH2	Yes	FJ612601.1			X	X	X	X	X
PepMV-SW	EU	No		Yes	EF408822		X	X	X	X
PepMV-No	EU	No		Yes	FJ612602		X	X	X	X
Le-00-347	EU	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Rode-8-2009	Peru	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Rode-9-2009	Peru	No		Yes	None	X	X			
EM-06-381	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Seigner-282	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Le-06-469	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Le-06-384	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Le-06-469	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Adam	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Rostock-#7	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Ve-07-Rode	EU	No		Yes	None	X	X			
Le-06-472	Ch2	No		Yes	None	X	X			
1066	EU	Yes	FJ940223							
DB1	EU	Yes	FJ940224							
Pep48	Ch2	Yes	not yet public							

Methods to accurately detect and diagnose PepMV

In WP3 a main deliverable is:

Deliverable 3.2:

To develop and evaluate methods to accurately detect and diagnose all relevant PepMV strains and isolates.

Since the first discovery of PepMV in the EU in 1999, many different detection methods and diagnostics have been developed to allow detection of viral infections in plant and seed material. Initially all were directed against the EU-tomato strains since this was the only strain present in the field. Several studies showed that the original Pepino strain (or Peruvian strain) was not present in the period before 2004 and analyses showed that all methods and diagnostics had sufficient cross-reactivity with this strain. This is not surprising given the very high levels of identity in both the overall genomic RNAs as well as the coat protein amino acid sequences.

After 2006 a new strain of PepMV called Chile-2 (Ch2) started spreading over Europe. For as yet unknown reasons Ch2 spread very fast within the EU and is now considered the predominant strain. However, isolates of the EU-tomato strain are still around and both strains can, and do occur in mixed infections in tomato crops.

Fairly recently in 2008 the previously described US1 strain was also detected in Europe (the Canary Islands). It is still unclear if, and to what extent, this strain has already spread to the main land of Europe. However, given previous experiences with Ch-2 one needs to consider the possibility of a rapid spread.

The presence of different strains and mixed infections means that truly reliable diagnostics should be able to detect all isolates of all strains. Possible contamination of seed lots with PepMV is also a serious issue since this would allow a fast spread of the virus. One infected seedling in several tens of thousands of young plants will result in serious crop infections. Sensitivity and specificity are therefore important criteria when evaluating methods for testing seed lots for PepMV.

Within the consortium several partners had already developed diagnostics both serological (a polyclonal antiserum by Partner #1) as well as molecular (different RT-PCR and RT-qPCR protocols; Partners #2, #10, #11, #20).

By partner #1 a study was performed in which a comparison was made between purified isolates of *Pepino mosaic virus* (PepMV) for their relative reactivity in a DAS-ELISA assay. Identical dilution series of five different PepMV isolates, belonging to three different virus strains were tested in healthy tomato leaf extract with polyclonal antisera from five different commercial suppliers.

All antisera tested detected all different strains, but there were minor differences in sensitivity, probably due to the isolates the antibodies were made against. These minor differences will not influence the detection of the different strains.

From this study it was decided by the consortium that the polyclonal antiserum as developed and produced by Prime Diagnostics was the best for serological detection of PepMV and would be the antiserum used in the ring test within WP4.

Different RT-PCR and RT-qPCR primer sets and protocols were evaluated by the different partners and choices were made on the most reliable and sensitive conventional (or end-point) RT-PCR and real-time quantitative RT-qPCR methods. In preparation for the ring test on PepMV diagnostics (WP4) the best were evaluated and finally included in a protocol book (see 3rd-year report) for use in the ring test (WP4, milestone 4.1) for the evaluation of the diagnostic methods.

Occurrence and spread of Pepino mosaic virus

In WP3 a main deliverable is:

Deliverable 3.3:

To determine the occurrence and spread of the different PepMV isolates and strains over the different EU member states.

All partners contributed to this deliverable by collecting information of the occurrence and distribution of the different PepMV isolates and strains in their respective countries (see third year report). In addition they collected information on the official status of PepMV in their country. This information was valuable input in the Pest Risk Analysis (PRA).

Pepino mosaic virus has been reported worldwide but it is often not clear from these reports and findings whether it can be considered established or not. It is not always easy to get a reliable picture of the exact distribution of the virus.

Information was collected from (scientific) literature and from the official survey data reported to the EC Standing Committee for Plant Health (SCPH) by the various member states. An overview of the available information for the different geographic regions is given below

1. Europe

Since 1999, PepMV has been reported as causing outbreaks of disease/being detected in 19 of the current 27 Member States (MS) of the EU; the first affected being the UK and the Netherlands, with sporadic reports from various countries since. (See below). The most recent information on the status of PepMV comes from the official EU surveys. Currently, the requirements for the surveys are for MS to survey 4 categories: tomato seed, plants for planting, fruit production sites and fruit being marketed. In reviewing the surveys it is important to note that not all MS appear to have reported to the EC or there are no data available, and, of those that have undertaken surveys, some have not reported on all 4 categories. The intensity of surveillance has also varied between years and MS. The summary below only reflects the overview reports from the EC either presented at the Standing Committee for Plant Health or in an overview table. More detailed information should be available from each EU MS but in general is not presented here because it was not available to the authors. According to survey reports from the EC Standing Committee for Plant Health (SCPH) presented on the 26th of May 2009, PepMV was reported as being detected in 9 out of 27 EU MS in 2007, while it was detected in 11 MS in 2008 (Anon., 2009b). In survey results for 2009 the virus was reported as being detected in 15 MS – the survey results are more detailed than those of the previous two years (Anon., 2010a). In the period 2007-2009 PepMV was found during official surveys in 17 MS: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Czech Republic (declared eradicated), Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Slovak Republic, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. The incidence of detection has varied between countries and years with some reports showing more prevalence of PepMV than others. In several EU countries where PepMV has been found, attempts have been made to eradicate the virus. Details are difficult to summarise as not all the information that is needed is freely available. All records are presumed to be in tomato.

2. EPPPO region:

As in Africa (Morocco) below and Europe (EU Member States) above plus:

- Canary Islands. Several reports (Jordá et al., 2001; Martínez-Culebras et al., 2002; Verhoeven et al., 2003). In the period 2003-2008 several findings on Gran Canaria and Tenerife (Alfaro-Fernandez et al., 2009a). The UK has intercepted tomato fruit from the Canary Islands infected with PepMV, most recently in the 2008 and 2009 official surveys (UK NPPO, 2008 and 2009). Sweden also detected infected fruit from Gran Canaria in their survey of marketed fruit in 2009 (Anon., 2010a).
- Israel. There are no published reports or official records of PepMV in Israel. However, the UK intercepted PepMV on 2 lots of seed out of 15 tested from Israel in the official survey of

2008 (UK NPPO, 2008). Also in 2009 found in seed during official surveys by Belgium (one lot) and France (five lots) (Anon., 2010a).

- Norway. Absent found once in 2001 and eradicated (EPPO, 2009).
- Switzerland. Found in 2004 in ‘the French-speaking part’ but then eradicated, other outbreaks have been found in Ticino and Zurich cantons (EPPO Alert List, 2009).
- Ukraine. (Verhoeven et al., 2003). Current status unknown.

3. Africa:

Morocco. Introduced into tomato crops in 2002 (Hanafia & Schnitzler, 2002). Current status unknown. However, the UK has intercepted tomato fruit from Morocco infected with PepMV most recently in the 2008 and 2009 official surveys (UK NPPO, 2008 and 2009). Poland has also detected fruit from Morocco infected with PepMV in the 2009 official survey (Anon., 2010a).

4. Americas

North America:

- Canada: First reported in 2001 (French et al., 2001). Since then several reports (Verhoeven et al., 2003; Ferguson, 2005; French et al., 2005; EPPO, 2009). A survey of greenhouse tomatoes in 2006 reports findings in the provinces British Columbia and Ontario (Ling et al., 2008).
- USA: First reported in 2001 (French et al., 2001). Since then several reports (Maroon-Lango et al., 2003; Verhoeven et al., 2003; Ling et al., 2008; EPPO, 2009). A survey of greenhouse tomatoes in 2006 reports findings in the states of Alabama, Arizona, California, Colorado and Texas (Ling et al., 2008). Tomato seed imported from the USA was tested and found to be positive for PepMV in the 2008 official UK survey (UK NPPO, 2008).

Central America:

- Guatemala: (EPPO, 2009) (current status unknown).

South America:

- Peru: PepMV was first discovered in 1974 in two field crops of pepino at Imperial in the Canete Valley of coastal Peru (Jones et al., 1980) and again in 2000 when it was also found in tomato and four wild *Lycopersicon* spp. (Soler et al., 2002); on the EPPO Alert List with no details (EPPO, 2009).
- Chile: On tomato (Muñoz et al., 2002 in Soler et al., 2005b) (EPPO Alert List, 2009 – no details).
- Ecuador: First report in Ecuador in surveys of *Lycopersicon* spp. detected PepMV in wild *Lycopersicon pimpinellifolium* (currant tomato) but not in tomato (Soler et al., 2005b); (EPPO, 2009 – no details). There are no details of the current status of PepMV in these countries.
- Caribbean: No record

4. Middle East:

- No record.

5. Asia:

- China. (Zhang et al., 2003). Current status unknown.

6. Oceania:

- No record.

Risk of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV

In WP3 a main deliverable is:

Deliverable 3.5:

To accurately determine the risk of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV within the EU.

Seed transmission

Since PepMV is such a contagious virus only one infected plant among tens of thousands of seedlings is a very serious threat which may easily lead to an entirely infected crop. The question whether PepMV can be transmitted through seed, and if so, to what extent, is therefore very relevant. One main objective of this WP was to accurately determine the risk of seed transmission of PepMV in the EU.

Production of 'infected' seed

During the kick-off meeting in Wageningen in May 2007 the decision was taken to use seeds that were available from a trial running at that moment at partner 10 (Belgium). Plants from the tomato variety Tricia, infected with a mixed PepMV isolate containing both the Tomato strain and the Chile 2 strain were used to harvest seeds. The fruits were harvested in the period July to October 2007 at three points in time: August 7th (week 32); September 4th (week 36); September 25th (week 39). Seed harvest was performed by the Belgian partner following a commercial seed harvesting procedure in compliance with ISHI and supplied by Syngenta Seeds (Bert Woudt). At each time point, all ripe tomatoes (500 to 800 tomatoes per harvest) from the plants infected with the mixed PepMV isolate were collected. Seeds were manually separated from the tomato pulp and collected in containers. The resulting volume of seeds and leftover pulp was diluted ½ with tap water. Subsequently, citric acid (pH 4, final ratio 1/15) and the enzyme pectinase (Pectinex, final concentration 0,25%) were added to the diluted pulp. During a 3 hour period, the mixture was incubated at 28°C and stirred every 30 minutes. Afterwards the seeds were separated from the

Figure 11: (a) sieving and rinsing of the harvested seeds. (b) seed transmission test : example partner 10 (ST). A sub batch of approx. 5000 seeds from the second seed harvesting (week 32) was sown in rockwool blocks (Cultilène) in a greenhouse department covered with insect nets. The seedlings were grouped in plots of 16. Leaf contact between seedlings of different blocks was prevented by spacing out the plots.

mixture by sieving and subsequently they were rinsed thoroughly with tap water (figure 11a). The seeds were centrifuged and washed again by rinsing with tap water. Finally, the seeds were centrifuged and dried during a 24h period in an oven at 26°C, with maximal ventilation. After drying the water content of the seeds was measured. Seeds were considered as ready for shipment when the water content was below 6%.

Each seed batch was shipped to the work package leader in Denmark (partner 6), accompanied by a letter of authority signed by both the Belgian and the Danish authorities. Further distribution to the different partners involved in the seed transmission trials was organised by the Danish partner. Partner 10 organized the availability of uninfected leaf material from the same tomato variety, to be used as negative controls in the ELISA testing, in collaboration with De Ruiter Seeds. De Ruiter Seeds (contact: Paul Maris) produced dried, virus free leaf material that was shipped directly to the Danish partner (partner 6) for further distribution among the partners.

Seed batch test for PepMV

A sample of tomato seeds (obtained from partner 10 in Belgium; third seed harvest: September 25th (week 39)) was tested by partner #7 (WUR Glastuinbouw) on to verify that PepMV was present in/on the seeds. A total of 15 samples (all from the same shipment) was tested, 10 seeds per sample. The seeds were crushed in a mixture of sand and water and inoculated on tobacco plants (*Nicotiana occidentalis* P1), using carborundum powder and cotton wool. Per sample, 2 plants were inoculated. Two weeks after inoculation, the symptoms on the plants were scored using the following score table: - no symptoms, +/- minor/ starting symptoms, + symptoms present, ++ severe symptoms. Although not all inoculated plants became infected the results showed that the virus on the seeds was indeed infectious. Similar results were obtained in a repetition of this test with 10 samples of 50 seeds each.

Seed transmission tests

Statistical analyses were performed to calculate how many seeds should be tested to obtain reliable and statistically sound results. Partner #3 calculated how many seeds are necessary to obtain a result with acceptable confidence intervals with three estimated infection rates: 1 %, 0,1 % and 0,01% and three number of seedlings per batch (10, 25 and 50). It was decided to test 100,000 seeds in batches of 10 were to be tested by ten different laboratories which would result in 1000 ELISA-tests to be done per laboratory.

Virus infected tomato seeds, produced by the Belgian partner in three batches of 40,000 - 50,000 seeds each (as described above) were mailed to partner 6 in Denmark, who coordinated the further dispatch of the seeds. Letters of Authority from the ten partners, who participated in the seed transmission tests, were obtained and infected seeds were dispatched.

Partners 6 (Denmark), 16 (Norway), 8 (Italy), 11 (Slovenia), 15 (Greece), 2 (UK), 17 (Bulgaria) carried out three glasshouse trials to assess seed transmission rate according to the agreed seed testing protocol (see below). Partner 18 (Portugal) and 14 (Poland) carried out two glasshouse tests and partner 10 (Belgium) carried out one glasshouse test. 4,000-5,000 seeds per trial were sown and 4-5 weeks after germination the plantlets were pooled ten by ten and presence of Pepino mosaic virus was tested by standard DAS-ELISA using Prime Diagnostics antibodies. The samples were stored for later confirmation tests by real time PCR.

Table 2: Numbers of positive pooled samples of 10 plants on the total number of pooled samples tested.

Partner	1 st test	2 nd test	3 rd test
Italy	1/249	1/393	1/410
Slovenia	0/71	0/153	2/240
Norway	0/346	0/350	2/411
Denmark	0/240	0/360	2/320
UK	0/329	0/365	2/348
Bulgaria	0/382	0/395	0/338
Greece	0/270	0/366	2/416
Belgium		2/311	
Portugal		0/350	3/350
Poland		0/495	5/520
Total	1/1887	3/3538	19/3353

Table 2 summarizes the results of the tests performed. A total of 87.780 plants grown from seeds harvested from PepMV infected plants have been tested in batches of 10 plants. Twenty-three pooled batches of plants were found positive in ELISA tests meaning that 23 seeds (one seed per pooled batch) gave rise to infected seedlings. These test data suggest a minimum transmission percentage of 0.026% depending on the time interval between the virus infection of the mother plant and the harvest of the seeds. The results show that seed transmission of PepMV occurs, though on a very low level and that use of seeds harvested from PepMV infected plants involves a risk of obtaining PepMV infected seedlings.

Conclusions

Results from the extensive grow-out trials performed in the framework of WP3 show that seed transmission of Pepino mosaic virus (PepMV) in tomato is possible, even though at a low level. A statistically sound estimation of 0,026% as the rate for PepMV transmission from tomato seeds to seedlings was obtained. The seed transmission rates differed from 0,005% to 0.057% depending on the time interval between PepMV infection and seed harvest. The infected seed batches were harvested from an artificially infected tomato crop and extracted by enzymatic treatment without subsequent disinfection. Infectivity assays on indicator plants confirmed the presence of viable virus particles on the seeds. Analyses of the seed batches using the ISHI-Veg approved immunological seed testing procedure, which is currently applied for screening commercial tomato seeds for PepMV contamination, revealed high concentrations of PepMV particles on the seeds from the infected batches. These results clearly show that the use of seeds harvested from PepMV infected plants bears the risk of obtaining PepMV infected seedlings, but also that PepMV contamination of tomato seeds can efficiently be traced by proper detection methods.

The seed transmission part was completed successfully and reported on in the first year project report. In addition the results were published in a common press release of PEPEIRA by the Coordinator in April 2008 and followed up by press releases in Denmark and Belgium.

A scientific paper of the results was written and accepted for publication by the European Journal of Plant Pathology. It was recently published as:

Hanssen IM, Mumford R, Blystad D-R, Cortez I, Hasiów-Jareszewska B, Hristova D, Pagán I, Pereira A-M, Peters J, Pospieszny H, Ravnikar M, Stijger I, Tomassoli L, Varveri C, van der Vlugt R, Nielsen SL, 2010. *Seed transmission of Pepino mosaic virus* in tomato. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* **126**, 145-152.

Table 3: Deliverables List WP3

List all deliverables, giving date of submission and any proposed revision to plans.

Del. no.	Deliverable name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Estimated indicative person-months	Used indicative person-months *)	Lead contractor
3.1	A report on the most important biological and genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains present in the different EU member states	3	M24	M36	6.5		1
3.2	An evaluation of methods to accurately detect and diagnose all relevant PepMV strains and isolates.	3	M36	M36	5		1
3.3	A report on the occurrence and spread of the different PepMV isolates and strains over the different EU member states.	3	M36	M36	4.2		1
3.4	An evaluation of the possible risks of PepMV strains and variants on tomato and other Solanaceous crops.	3	M36	M36	4.2		1
3.5	An evaluation of the possible risk of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV within the EU	3	M36	M36	22		1

*) if available

Table 4: Milestones List WP3

List all milestones, giving date of achievement and any proposed revision to plans.

Milestone No.	Milestone name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Lead contractor
3.1	A representative collection of isolates of PepMV from across EU	3	M33	M33	1
3.2	A biological comparison of PepMV isolates collected	3	M24	M30	1
3.3	An assessment of seed transmission of PepMV	3	M36	M18	1
3.4	An assessment of occurrence and spread of PepMV in EU member states	3	M36	M36	1
3.5	Assays for the accurate detection and discrimination of PepMV strains	3	M36	M36	1

All deliverables and Milestones have been completed and reached.

WP 4: Risk assessment and diagnostic protocol

Deliverables

- 4.1. A Europe wide Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) for PepMV
- 4.2. An EPPO protocol for the detection of PepMV

The objective of the final work package of the project was to evaluate and validate the scientific data and methods generated in work packages 2 and 3, in order to:

- Carry out a ring test of PepMV diagnostic methods and to use this data to;
- Write an EPPO protocol containing methods for the detection and diagnosis of PepMV
- Produce a revised EU-wide PRA for PepMV

In the third year of the project a set of diagnostic protocols was selected from those developed and evaluated earlier in WP3. This work is described in more detail in the previous annual project reports. The selected set of protocols, covering biological, serological and molecular tests, was evaluated by partners #1, #2 and #20 on the material that was to be used in the methods ring test. All protocols performed very well and it was concluded that the methods were suited for the ring test. They were compiled in a protocol book that was subsequently used in a methods ring test.

Isolates from the four main strains of PepMV were propagated by partner #1 for use in the ring test. In addition, tomato seeds infected with the four PepMV strains were propagated by partner #7 and all seed batches (healthy and infected) were prepared by partner #20. All material, i.e. virus isolates, healthy and infected seed batches, antiserum, RT-PCR primers and probes, were distributed among the 21 participants of the ring test. In addition to most project partners also three seed companies, as representatives of the Int. Seed Health Initiative (ISHI) participated in the ring test.

PepMV diagnostics Ring test

Since a low seed transmission rate has been demonstrated for PepMV (see WP report and Hansen et al, 2010) and infected tomato seedlings typically do not show symptoms, long distance spread of PepMV is thought to be through contaminated seeds or infected transplants. To prevent or reduce further spread of PepMV this virus has become a regulated pest on tomato seeds in EU countries because of emergency decision EU directive 2004/200/EC. For this reason it was logical that the PEPEIRA ring tests should evaluate the suitability of methods for detecting PepMV on tomato seeds. Consequently, the consortium decided to focus the ring tests on PepMV detection on/in tomato seeds and to use PepMV-infected leaf tissue only as positive controls.

Therefore, the ring tests consisted basically of:

- DAS-ELISA plus bioassay followed by ELISA
- EP RT-PCR plus bioassay followed by ELISA
- TaqMan assay plus bioassay followed by ELISA

Irrespective of the type of ring-test method, participating laboratories had to analyse the same number and types of samples and to use each sub-sample for mechanical inoculation of 2 *N. benthamiana* or *N. occidentalis*.

Table 1: Types of samples to be analyzed by ELISA, end-point RT-PCR and TaqMan assay

Spiking ratio	Tomato seeds contaminated with PepMV strains				Clean seeds	PepMV-infected leaves	Buffer
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru			
1: 50 [5 + 245]	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x4)	(2x1)	(2x1)
1 : 250	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)			
1 : 1,250	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)			
1 : 6,250	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)	(2x1)			

Each ring-test participant was provided with two sets of samples and asked to analyze these two sets in two separate experiments at a time interval of 4-7 days. This allowed participants to make up for possible deficiencies and/or problems that may have occurred in the analysis of the first set of samples.

Sequence of steps to be followed by ring-test participants:

- day 1*:	Sow seeds of indicator plants
- 4-6 weeks later (when test plants are at the right stage for sap inoculation):	Prepare seed extracts and use them for bioassay (sap inoculation) and laboratory tests (ELISA, end-point RT-PCR and/or TaqMan assay)
- 1 day later:	Collect and analyze all ELISA, end-point RT-PCR and/or TaqMan assay data
- 6, 10 and 14 days later:	Inspect indicator plants for symptom development at 4-day intervals
- 2 to 3 weeks later:	Use ELISA or RT-PCR for analyzing all inoculated indicator plants

* Sow seeds at a given time interval if the duplicate seed samples are to be analyzed in two separate experiments spaced a few days apart.

Ring test results

Twenty laboratories (17 PEPEIRA partners and 3 seed companies) conducted bioassays as described in the “Ring Test Protocol Booklet”; i.e. they assayed the infectivity of seed extracts on test plants (*N. occidentalis* 37B or *N. benthamiana*) followed about two weeks later by DAS-ELISA analysis of all the test plants inoculated. A total of 22 data sets were received: 4 from 2 labs detailing the results for each of the two sample sets and 18 from 18 labs summarizing the results for the 2 sets supplied. Overall, 15 of the 20 labs had clearly negative bioassay results, even though one lab did not do ELISA on test plants inoculated with seed extracts diluted higher than 1:50. Of the remaining 5 labs, one lab apparently had a contamination problem or mixed up samples (Fig. 1, panel 4), one lab claimed to have had ‘bioassay positives’ based on questionable (actually negative!) ELISA reactions, and only three labs had clearly positive bioassay results (Fig. 1, panels 1, 2, 3).

Figure 1: Number of bioassay-positive test plants

1	PepMV strain				PO4 buffer	clean seeds
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru		
					0	0
1: 50	2	0	0	0		
1: 250	2	0	0	0		
1:1250	2	0	0	0		
1:6250	1	0	0	0		

2	PepMV strain				PO4 buffer	clean seeds
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru		
					0	0
1: 50	0	2	0	0		
1: 250	0	2	0	0		
1:1250	0	0	0	0		
1:6250	0	0	0	0		

3	PepMV strain				PO4 buffer	clean seeds
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru		
					0	0
1: 50	0	0	0	1		
1: 250	0	0	0	0		
1:1250	0	0	0	0		
1:6250	0	0	0	0		

4	PepMV strain				PO4 buffer	clean seeds
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru		
					0	1
1: 50	0	0	0	0		
1: 250	0	0	0	0		
1:1250	0	0	0	1		
1:6250	0	0	0	0		

The bioassay results were based on a total of about 1680 test plants (*N. occidentalis* 37B [or *N. benthamiana*]) inoculated by the ring-test participants, with only 12 test plants (0.7%) being shown to be infected by PepMV. This means that only three (1.9%) of the 160 seed samples containing PepMV-contaminated seeds were shown to contain infectious PepMV virions.

In earlier tests by partner 1 (results not shown), *N. occidentalis* 37B was shown to be a very sensitive indicator plant for all strains of PepMV with a similar level of sensitivity for the presence of PepMV as the DAS-ELISA. In addition it should be remarked that nearly all labs participating in the bioassays are plant virology labs very experienced in working with indicator plants.

This surprisingly low infectivity rate for tomato seeds spiked with freshly harvested seeds originating from PepMV-infected plants raises several questions, such as:

- Why were the concentrations of infectious PepMV virions so low?
- Did the Pectinex treatment under acidic conditions (\pm pH 4) affect PepMV infectivity?
- Is a bioassay sufficiently reliable for detecting infectious PepMV and for assessing the appropriateness and effectiveness of an acid treatment of tomato seeds as required by EU directive 2004/200/EC?

With respect to false negatives and positives, we can confidently state that only one sample in one of 20 labs gave a 'false positive' result. However, we do not know to what extent 'false negative' results were obtained. This could not be assessed as there is no alternative test available for determining the infectivity of seed samples.

ELISA

Eighteen laboratories (15 PEPEIRA partners and 3 seed companies) conducted DAS-ELISA as described in the "Ring Test Protocol Booklet"; i.e. they analyzed the seed extracts for detectable amounts of PepMV antigen by DAS-ELISA. A total of 35 data sets were received: 34 from 17 labs detailing the ELISA results for each of the two sample sets and 1 from 1 lab providing ELISA data for only 1 set of the 2 sets supplied.

Partner 1 analysed the ELISA data and tried to find a way to present the results as clearly as possible (Table 7). Two things were very clear:

- Not unexpectedly, there were huge differences in the ELISA results between partners (not illustrated).

- Up to a dilution of 1:1,250 the majority of ELISA reactions were clearly positive. Only at 1:6250 the overall results became less clear but they varied greatly between labs as the sensitivity clearly depended on the lab doing the test.
- All 4 PepMV strains were readily detected.
- All four concentrations were detected.

Table 7. Percentage of ELISA-positive reactions of extracts from seed samples spiked with seeds originating from plants infected with the PepMV strains EU, Ch2, US1 and Peru

PepMV strain	Dilution of seed extract			
	1: 50	1: 250	1:1,250	1:6,250
EU	97	94	77	56
Ch2	100	97	96	86
US1	97	94	80	57
Peru	94	87	84	44

Figure 2. Numbers and percentages of true and false positive and negative DAS-ELISA results

		'True'	
		+	-
ELISA	+	939 (83.8%)	1 (0.4%)
	-	181 (16.2%)	283 (99.6%)
		1120	284

With respect to false negatives and positives DAS-ELISA results (Fig. 2), there was only one lab where a false positive occurred; for instance, the healthy control values were higher than those of the positive control supplied. The majority of the false negative DAS-ELISA results were probably due to the fact that some labs had problems with overall sensitivity.

End-point (EP) RT-PCR

Fourteen laboratories (13 PEPEIRA partners and 1 seed company) conducted EP RT-PCR as described in the “Ring Test Protocol Booklet”; i.e. they analyzed seed extracts for detectable amounts of PepMV RNA. A total of 28 data sets were received: 26 complete sets from 13 labs detailing the ELISA results for each of the two sample sets and 2 incomplete sets from 1 lab which did not test the 1:50 dilution of sample set B.

From the analysis of the EP RT-PCR data by partner 20, a few things became clear:

- All 4 strains were readily detected (by most labs)
- All 4 concentrations were detected (by only few labs)
- The two highest dilutions were often not detected
- Although no internal control was used for EP RT-PCR, the results from the TaqMan assay, which included a COX assay, suggest that the use of the RNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen) for RNA extraction from tomato seeds performed well.

The most striking observation here was that the sensitivity and specificity of EP RT-PCR varied enormously between individual labs, with 7 of 14 labs failing to detect most strains at higher dilutions and obtaining no or only weakly even positive controls provided [or they reacted only weakly]. In contrast, in the 7 other labs EP RT-PCR performed very well, giving very specific reactions and permitting very sensitive detection of PepMV similar to that observed for DAS-ELISA and even qRT-PCR. These striking differences between labs are illustrated by two contrasting examples shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Figure 3. EP RT-PCR results* obtained in two labs

Lab X							
Seed batch A	PepMV strain				clean seeds	pos ctrl	buffer
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru			
					0	+	0
1:50	++	+++	+++	++			
1:250	0	0	++	+			
1:1250	+	+	+	0			
1:6250	0	0	0	0			

Seed batch B	PepMV strain				clean seeds	pos ctrl	buffer
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru			
					0	0	0
1:50	+	+++	+	+			
1:250	0	+++	0	+++			
1:1250	++	++	0	0			
1:6250	0	+	0	0			

Lab Y							
Seed batch A	PepMV strain				clean seeds	pos ctrl	buffer
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru			
					0	+++	0
1:50	+++	+++	++	++			
1:250	+++	+++	++	++			
1:1250	+++	+++	++	++			
1:6250	++	+++	++	+			

Seed batch B	PepMV strain				clean seeds	pos ctrl	buffer
	EU	Ch2	US1	Peru			
					0	++	0
1:50	+++	+++	+	+			
1:250	+++	+++	+	+			
1:1250	++	+++	+	+			
1:6250	+	+++	+	+			

* EP RT-PCR reactions were classed as strong (+++), intermediate (++), weak (+), and negative (0).

Figure 4. EP RT-PCR products obtained in two labs (other than those shown in Fig. 3) with RNA extracts from one of the two sample sets provided

With respect to false negatives and positives EP RT-PCR results (Fig. 5), there was only one lab where a false positive occurred. This was probably due to an accidental sample switch. The high number of ‘false negatives’ (165 = 37%) definitely resulted from the sensitivity and specificity problems encountered in 7 of the 14 labs when trying to use the RT-PCR method described in the “Ring-Test Protocol Booklet” (WP3).

Figure 5. Numbers and percentages of true and false positive and negative EP RT-PCR results

		‘True’	
		+	-
EP RT-PCR	+	283 (63.2%)	1 (0.9%)
	-	165 (36.8%)	111 (99.1%)
		448	112

qRT-PCR (TaqMan assay)

Eleven laboratories (8 PEPEIRA partners and 3 seed companies) conducted qRT-PCR as described in the “Ring Test Protocol Booklet”; i.e. they analyzed the seed extracts for amounts of PepMV antigen detectable by a TaqMan assay. A total of 19 data sets were received: 16 from 8 labs detailing the TaqMan results for each of the two sample sets and 3 from 3 labs providing TaqMan data for only 1 set of the 2 sets supplied.

The TaqMan assay data analysed by partner 2 indicated the following:

- All 4 strains were readily detected.
- All 4 concentrations were readily detected.
- Extraction procedure performed extremely well, as no failures were seen when assessed using COX assay.

With respect to false negatives and positives TaqMan assay results (Fig. 6), there were only two labs where false positives occurred (2 out of 76 healthy samples; 2.6%). It was strongly suspected that at least one was due to an accidental sample switch as the adjacent sample number was false negative and all other results were correct.

‘False negatives’ (39 = 13%) were observed for 4 labs, as follows:

- 1 lab had issue with overall sensitivity: it detected all strains but not at higher dilutions, with the Peruvian strain being worst (1:50 only).
- 1 lab failed to detect any Ch2 or Peruvian positives.
- 1 lab failed to detect any Peruvian positives.
- 1 lab only detected one Peruvian 1:50 positive (out of 8).

Figure 6. Numbers and percentages of true and false positive and negative qRT-PCR (TaqMan) results

		‘True’	
		+	-
TaqMan	+	265 (87.2%)	2 (2.6%)
	-	39 (12.8%)	74 (97.4%)
		304	76

Ring test Conclusions

The results of the ring tests can be summarized as follows:

- ▶ Both the developed DAS-ELISA and qRT-PCR protocols are very sensitive and robust tests for the detection of all PepMV strains on tomato seeds. Both methods worked well in nearly all participating labs and appear to be comparable in terms of reliability and sensitivity. Both methods can be recommended for the detection of PepMV on tomato seeds.
- ▶ Following the end point RT-PCR protocol, 7 of the 14 participating labs encountered problems (lack of sensitivity; unspecific reactions). The reasons for this remain unclear. In contrast to these negative results, in the other 7 labs the protocol worked excellent permitting both sensitive and specific detection of PepMV. Although potentially a sensitive and robust test, the EP RT-PCR method should be used with caution and ample and proper positive and negative controls should be included.
- ▶ A bio-assay (i.e. inoculation of a sample on a suitable indicator plant) is generally regarded as a sensitive method for the detection of viable virus. In this ring test however, the results from the bio assays of the different samples are in sharp contrast to the results obtained for both the ELISA and qRT-PCR (Taqman) assays for the same samples. Of all samples that were clearly positive in ELISA and TaqMan, and thus were contaminated with PepMV, only a very small fraction proved infectious on the indicator plants. It is therefore not clear what the significance of the bio assays results is. Given these results it is recommended that the bio-assay for the presence of infectious PepMV should be used with caution.

Figure 7. Numbers and percentages of true and false positive and negative results in DAS-ELISA, EP RT-PCR and qRT-PCR (TaqMan)

		‘True’ (in %)					
		+			-		
		ELISA	EP RT-PCR	TaqMan	ELISA	EP RT-PCR	TaqMan
+	83.8	63.2	87.2	0.4	0.9	2.6	
-	16.2	36.8	12.8	99.6	99.1	97.4	
	(1120)	(448)	(304)	(284)	(112)	(76)	

Based on the evaluated diagnostic protocols a draft EPPO diagnostic protocol (DP) was written for the detection of PepMV, which will be presented to EPPO for approval. Since this DP is impossible to summarize it is not presented here. It can be found in the third year report and will eventually be published on the pepeira web site.

A Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) for PepMV was written based on all information gathered within the project as well as additionally available information from literature, NPPOs and surveys. This PRA describes a detailed analysis and assessment of all factors that may contribute to the possible risks of PepMV. As for the DP also the PRA is a elaborate document (132 pages). The PRA can be found in the third year project report.

Table 1: Deliverables List WP4

List all deliverables, giving date of submission and any proposed revision to plans.

Del. no.	Deliverable name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Estimated indicative person-months	Used indicative person-months *)	Lead contractor
4.1	A Europe wide Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) for PepMV	4	M36	M36	12	0	20
4.2	An EPPO protocol for the detection of PepMV	4	M36	M36	2.25	0	20

*) if available

Table 2: Milestones List WP4

List all milestones, giving date of achievement and any proposed revision to plans.

Milestone no.	Milestone name	Workpackage no.	Date due	Actual delivery date	Lead contractor
4.1	Complete ring test of diagnostic methods in all participating member states and selected associated states	4	M36	M36	20
4.2	Completion of EPPO protocol and submission to EPPO	4	M360	M36	20
4.3	Completion of Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) and submission to SCPH	4	M36	M36	19

Section 2 Dissemination and use

- An EPPO protocol for the reliable and sensitive detection of PepMV has been prepared by the consortium. This protocol will be submitted to EPPO for further evaluation. If approved this protocol will serve as the standard for detection of PepMV within the EU by all testing bodies.
- A Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) on PepMV has been prepared by the consortium. This PRA will be submitted to the Standing Committee on Plant Health and can be used by the commission for regulatory decisions with regard to PepMV.
- An economic model to calculate the impact of PepMV on the level of individual countries has been developed. This model will be made available to the public through the PEPEIRA web site.
- ST was responsible (first author) for three scientific publications: (1) a paper on the PEPEIRA seed transmission results which was written in collaboration with the PEPEIRA partners involved in the seed transmission trials, (2) a paper on interactions of different PepMV isolates in collaboration with PEPEIRA partner 11, and (3) a review article on PepMV:
 1. Hanssen IM, Mumford R, Blystad D-R, Cortez I, Hasiów-jareszewska B, Hristova D, Pagán I, Pepeira A-M, Peters J, Pospieszny H, Ravnikař M, Stijger I, Tomassoli L, Varveri C, van der Vlught R, Nielsen SL, 2010. Seed transmission of Pepino mosaic virus in tomato. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 126: 145-152.
 2. Hanssen IM, Gutiérrez-Aguirre I, Paeleman A, Goen K, Wittemans L, Lievens B, Vanachter ACRC, Ravnikař M, Thomma BPHJ, 2010. Cross-protection or enhanced symptom display in greenhouse tomato co-infected with different Pepino mosaic virus isolates. *Plant Pathol.* 59: 13-21.
 3. Hanssen IM, Thomma BPHJ, 2010. Pepino mosaic virus: a successful pathogen that rapidly emerged from emerging to endemic in tomato crops. *Mol. Plant Pathol.* 11: 179-189.
- A real time qPCR method diagnostic method that can distinguish among different PepMV strains was described and validated and an article was published in 2009, “Real-time quantitative PCR based sensitive detection and genotype discrimination of Pepino mosaic virus” *Journal of Virological Methods* 162 (2009) 46–55. Partners involved (2 and 11).
- IOR (partner 14) was author or co-author of the following scientific publications
 1. Hasiów B., N. Borodynko, H. Pospieszny. 2008. Complete genome RNA sequence of the Polish Pepino mosaic virus isolate belonging to the US2 strain. *Virus Genes*, vol. 36(1): 209-214 (IF =1,362)
 2. Pospieszny H., B. Hasiów, N. Borodynko. 2008. Characterization of two distinct Polish isolates of Pepino mosaic virus. *Eur J Plant Pathol* 36(1): 443-445 (IF=1,482)
 3. Hasiów B., N. Borodynko, H. Pospieszny. 2008. Development of a real time RT-PCR assay for detecting genetically different Pepino mosaic virus isolates. *Journal of Plant Protection Research* 48(3) 295-301.
 4. Hasiów-Jaroszewska B., Borodynko N., Pospieszny H. 2009. Infectious RNA transcripts derived from cloned cDNA of a pepino mosaic virus isolate. *Archives of Virology* 154: 853- 856. (IF 2,02)
 5. Hasiów-Jaroszewska B., Pospieszny H., Borodynko N. 2009. New necrotic isolates of Pepino mosaic virus representing Ch2 genotype. *Journal of Phytopathology* 157 (7-8) 494-496 (IF 0,868).
 6. Hasiów-Jaroszewska B., H. Pospieszny, N. Borodynko, N. Rymelska 2009. Przenoszenie PepMV z nasionami pomidora. *Progress of Plant Protection* 49(2) 637-640.
- A scientific review paper was written by the coordinator (René van der Vlught) on PepMV and published in June 2009 in the “Hellenic Plant Protection Journal”, (ISSN 1791-3691) the new scientific publication of the Benaki Phytopathological Institute (Athens, Greece) replacing the *Annals of the Benaki Phytopathological Institute* (ISSN 1790-1480) which had been published since 1935. The review article is accessible electronically at the Institute’s website.
- A scientific paper on the results of the biological characterization of the different PepMV strains on the Solanaceous host plants is in preparation by partners #6, 16 and 1.
- A scientific review paper on PepMV and the outcome of the Pepeira project will be written on invitation for publication in *Annals of Applied Biology* by partner #1.

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

1.1 Collated period activity report

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

1.2 Final project report

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

1.3 Website, including a secure area accessible by all partners and a public area for general dissemination

Due date of deliverable: Month 6

Actual submission date: Month 6

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	X
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

1.4 30th Month symposia programs

Due date of deliverable: Month 30

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

1.5 Project presentation

Due date of deliverable: Month 6

Actual submission date: Month 6

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe’s natural resources

2.1 Completed glasshouse trials over two seasons on four different locations

Due date of deliverable: Month 34

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	X
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

2.2 Assessment of impact of PepMV on infected tomato crops

Due date of deliverable: Month 34

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	X
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

2.3 Econometric model for assessing economic impact

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	X
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

2.4 Cost benefit analysis of PepMV control measures

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

3.1 A report on the most important biological and genetic characteristics of the different PepMV isolates and strains present in the different EU member states.

Due date of deliverable: Month 24

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

3.2 An evaluation of methods to accurately detect and diagnose all relevant PepMV strains and isolates

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	X
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

3.3 A report on the occurrence and spread of the different PepMV isolates and strains over the different EU member states

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe’s natural resources

3.4 An evaluation of the possible risks of PepMV strains and variants on tomato and other Solaneceous crops

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X?
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

3.5 An evaluation of the possible risk of seed transmission in the spread of PepMV within the EU

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X?
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

4.1 A Europe wide Pest Risk Analysis (PRA) for PepMV

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Project no. 44189

PEPEIRA

Pepino mosaic virus: *epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis.*

SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH OR INNOVATION PROJECT

Thematic Priority Sustainable management of Europe's natural resources

4.2 An EPPO protocol for the detection of PepMV

Due date of deliverable: Month 36

Actual submission date: Month 36

Start date of project: 01 february 2007

Duration: 3 years

Plant Research International

[final version]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme (2002-2006)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	